

Real and synthetic scenarios generated for the development, training, virtual testing and validation of CCAM systems

SYNERGIES

Data formats, fusion, data compression and Semantic Framework

Document Type	Document, report
Document Number	D4.1
Primary Author(s)	Karlo Horvat AVL List GmbH
Document Version / Status	1.3 Final version
Distribution Level	PU (public)

Project Acronym	SYNERGIES
Project Website	www.synergies-ccam.eu
Project Coordinator	IDIADA AUTOMOTIVE TECHNOLOGY SA
Grant Agreement Number	101146542
Date of latest version of Annex I against which the assessment will be made	2024-05-27

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

CONTRIBUTORS

Name	Organization
Itziar Urbietta	Vicomtech
Karlo Horvat	AVL
Jobst Beckmann	IKA
Patrick Irvine	UoW
Clement Val	CEESAR
Ludwig Friedmann	BMW
Erwan Revert	IRTSX
Didier Wright	IRTSX
Ilma Okanovic	ViF
Jerein Jeyachandran	UoW
Aitor Iglesias Hernández	Vicomtech
Arnaud Sibenaler	CEESAR
Peter Koval	Vicomtech

FORMAL REVIEWERS

Name	Organization	Date
Riccardo Berta	UNIGE	2026-05-18
Jordi Pont	Applus+ IDIADA	2026-05-29

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Revision	Date	Author Organization	Description
0.1	2025-11-13	Itziar Urbietta (VICOM)	Ontology Manager Tool and Tool Ontology sections
0.2	2025-12-16	Karlo Horvat (AVL)	Table of figures and a table of captions
0.3	2025-12-17	Karlo Horvat (AVL)	First review
0.4	2025-12-23	Karlo Horvat (AVL)	Final preliminary version
1.0	2026-05-12	Karlo Horvat (AVL)	Version for internal review (pre-peer review)
1.1	2026-05-13	Karlo Horvat (AVL)	Updated version for internal review (pre-peer review)
1.2	2026-05-19	Riccardo Berta (UNIGE)	Peer review version
1.3	2026-05-29	Karlo Horvat (AVL)	Final version (after peer review)

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
2	OBJECTIVES	8
3	DESCRIPTION OF WORK	9
3.1	Introduction	9
3.2	Relation to other SYNERGIES Activities	9
3.3	Data formats	10
3.3.1	Requirements on Scenario Source Data	11
3.3.2	OMEGA-PRIME Specification	12
3.4	Semantic framework	14
3.4.1	Data journeys and tools	15
3.4.2	Ontology definition	21
3.4.3	Ontology catalogue for Scenario generation	21
3.4.4	Taxonomies	22
3.4.5	Tool Ontology	24
3.4.6	Ontology Manager Tool	32
3.5	Overview of Partner Contributions to Detection, Tracking, Fusion, and Scenario Representation	37
3.5.1	CEESAR	37
3.5.2	Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH	42
3.5.3	Vicomtech	52
4	CONCLUSIONS	60
5	REFERENCES	61
A.	ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS	63

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 Work package relations	10
Figure 2 Process steps for the generation of Scenario Source Data	11
Figure 3 OMEGA-PRIME file structure	13
Figure 4 Data Collection Journey AVL	15
Figure 5 ASAM OpenLABEL scenario tagging class hierarchy and layered tagging model, illustrating the coverage of existing standards (OpenODD, OpenXOntology, BSI PAS 1883) and the boundaries of their term coverage at the application level.....	23
Figure 6 Class hierarchy of the SYNERGIES Tool Ontology.....	27
Figure 7 Subclass hierarchy of Metadata in the SYNERGIES Tool Ontology.....	28
Figure 8 Object properties of the SYNERGIES Tool ontology.....	29
Figure 9 Data properties of the SYNERGIES Tool ontology.....	30
Figure 10 Ontology Manager functional architecture	33
Figure 11 Snippet of ontology extension for Human showing sub-classes and properties on Protege.....	36
Figure 12 Processing pipeline	37
Figure 13 Boulevard de la Vilette, Paris, Preprocessed point cloud and front image	39
Figure 14 Point cloud map with PCRS map of the data collection area.....	39
Figure 15 Result of the localization pipeline on one record.....	40
Figure 16 Manually annotated frame	41
Figure 17 Data Modify tap with Trajectory Reconstruction section enclosed within the red rectangle. Upon selection of the hyperparameter values, the reconstruction is initiated clicking on Start button (bottom right).....	46
Figure 18 Demonstration of the results for the measurements corrupted with noise of Gaussian profile.....	47
Figure 19 Demonstration of the results for the measurements corrupted with outliers	48
Figure 20 Demonstration of the results for the measurements containing time gaps	48
Figure 21 Demonstration of results for measurements containing all three expected challenges (noise, outliers, and time gaps)	49
Figure 22 Kinematic tracker	57

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 Tool vocabulary.....	16
Table 2 Tool specification template.....	17
Table 3 Tool specification example.....	18
Table 4 Object properties definition.....	29
Table 5 Data properties definition.....	30
Table 6 Data format class instances.....	31
Table 7 Data Converter class instances.....	31
Table 8 Labelling tool class instances.....	32
Table 9 Loss function parameters.....	50

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents outcomes of work performed under Task 4.1 and Task 4.2, addressing interoperability, semantic integration, and efficient data handling for advanced data processing in mobility and traffic systems. The overarching objective is to establish trustworthy, effective, and scalable solutions that transform complex, heterogeneous traffic and scenario data into reliable, machine-readable information suitable for scenario generation, simulation, and validation.

The work progressed through coordinated activities aimed at harmonizing data representations and enabling seamless interaction between tools and data sources, in alignment with WP2 specifications. Task 4.1 focused on the design and implementation of ontologies and a semantic framework to support consistent semantic description across diverse data sources, including vehicles, stationery and semi-stationary infrastructure, and multiple sensor modalities (e.g. camera, LiDAR). The adoption and extension of established standards such as ASAM and ISO enable interoperable data exchange and support the representation of intricate urban and rural scenarios.

Building on this semantic foundation, Task 4.2 addressed the challenge of data fusion and semantic compression in extended complex scenarios characterized by dense spatio-temporal dynamics and numerous interacting elements. This work emphasizes the use of semantic abstractions and cross-domain vocabularies to efficiently encode scenario information while preserving machine readability, interpretability, and relevance for downstream processing. The resulting models facilitate compact representations that support efficient handling, replay, and reuse of scenarios within simulation environments, and enable effective integration of heterogeneous data sources.

Key achievements include:

- **Ontology Catalogue:** A curated collection of ontologies from European initiatives and standards, supporting reuse and semantic alignment across tools and domains.
- **Tool Specification Template:** A standardized template for describing tools, enabling consistent characterization of inputs, outputs, and capabilities.
- **Tool Vocabulary and Ontology:** A formal semantic representation of tools and their metadata, supporting automated reasoning and interoperability.
- **Ontology Management Service:** A functional service enabling ontology storage, querying, and semantic operations within the framework.
- **Semantic Data Fusion and Compression Models:** Concepts and methods that combine data fusion with semantic abstraction to reduce data volume while maintaining expressiveness and interpretability in complex scenarios.

The outcomes of Tasks 4.1 and 4.2 comprise a combination of implemented results and conceptual specifications that together form the foundation for subsequent developments within WP4. For clarity, the maturity of the presented artefacts is distinguished as follows:

- **Implemented results (developed and validated within T4.1 and T4.2):**

The Ontology Catalogue, Tool Specification Template, Tool Vocabulary and Tool Ontology, and the Ontology Management Service have been designed and realized as functional components. These artefacts provide concrete mechanisms for semantic interoperability, including ontology reuse, tool description, metadata representation, and ontology management operations, and have been validated within the project as operational prototypes.

- Methodological and conceptual results (specified and demonstrated at concept level):

The Semantic Data Fusion and Compression Models represent methodological contributions and conceptual frameworks. These define approaches for combining heterogeneous data sources and applying semantic abstraction to reduce data complexity. While demonstrated on representative scenarios, they are not yet implemented as fully integrated toolchains.

- Future developments (to be addressed in subsequent WP4 tasks):

Building on the foundations established in this deliverable, subsequent tasks in WP4 (notably T4.3–T4.5) will focus on the implementation of ontology-based semantic data processing tools, explainable AI-enabled semantic processing, and visualization and annotation services. These activities will operationalize the semantic framework, data formats, and processing concepts developed in T4.1 and T4.2 into fully deployable tools, as further detailed in D4.2 and later deliverables.

Together, these results establish a coherent semantic interoperability framework that supports both tool integration and efficient management of complex scenario data. This framework forms a critical enabler for scalable and trustworthy AI-driven workflows for scenario generation, simulation, and validation, and provides a solid foundation for subsequent activities in scenario execution and synthetic data generation.

Keywords: Ontology, Semantic Framework, Tool Vocabulary, Data Interoperability, Semantic Data Fusion, Data Compression, Ontology Management

2 OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this deliverable align with the SYNERGIES vision of enabling trustworthy AI-driven scenario generation and WP4's mission to establish interoperable data processing tools. Specifically, Task 4.1 aimed to:

- Design and implement a semantic framework to support interoperability between heterogeneous tools and data sources.
- Investigate and document tools relevant for data processing and scenario generation, ensuring compliance with WP2 specifications.
- Develop supporting resources, including an Ontology Catalogue, Tool Vocabulary, and Tool Specification Template, to streamline integration and enhance semantic capabilities.

Complementing this work, the objectives of Task 4.2 were to:

- Enable semantic data fusion and compression for extended and complex scenarios involving rich spatio-temporal dynamics and numerous interacting elements.
- Investigate modelling techniques and semantic abstractions that allow efficient, machine-readable representation of complex scenario data while preserving interpretability.
- Build upon existing vocabularies and cross-domain concepts to ensure reusability, modularity, and effective inter-domain communication.
- Support the efficient replay and reuse of processed data and scenarios within simulation environments, enabling downstream scenario execution and synthetic data generation activities.

Initially, Task 4.1 included the provision of a dedicated ontology for WP5. However, following project-level alignment, this objective was revised to avoid duplication of efforts and potential fragmentation. The responsibility for developing the scenario-level ontology was therefore assigned to WP5, which adopted and extended existing standards (notably OpenXOntology) as the basis for scenario representation. Consequently, Task 4.1 shifted its focus toward tool investigation, semantic framework development, and the creation of supporting resources such as the Ontology Catalogue. This catalogue provides a structured overview of relevant ontologies and standards, which can be consulted by other work packages, including WP5, to support awareness and alignment.

In this context, WP4 focuses on the semantic description of tools and interoperability mechanisms, while WP5 defines the semantic representation of scenarios. This separation of concerns ensures consistency across the project while reducing overlap and mitigating the risk of ontology fragmentation. The alignment between both work packages is further reflected in the ontology-related considerations presented in Deliverable D5.1 [1].

This work contributes to WP4 objectives by:

- Establishing trustworthy, effective, and interoperable data processing tools.
- Enabling semantic integration and traceability through harmonized metadata and tool specifications.
- Supporting scenario variability and data quality assurance via structured tool information.

These objectives collectively lay the groundwork for integrated, interoperable workflows capable of handling complex real-world scenarios across the SYNERGIES toolchain.

3 DESCRIPTION OF WORK

3.1 Introduction

Developing a semantic framework involves a structured set of efforts aimed at enabling interoperability, traceability, and meaningful integration of heterogeneous data and tools.

The activities under Task 4.1 can be grouped into four main phases:

- Data Format Harmonization

A Data Format Working Group was established to analyse and harmonize data formats across the project. This effort ensured consistency with WP2 specifications and laid the foundation for interoperability between heterogeneous data sources.

- Ontology and Semantic Framework Development

An Ontology Catalogue was created, consolidating ontologies from other EU projects and making them accessible online. This Catalogue consists of ontologies used for scenario generation. This resource supports semantic consistency and promotes reuse of established standards.

- Tool Investigation and Specification

A Tool Specification Template was developed and distributed to partners, enabling the collection of essential tool information such as functionalities, input/output formats, and compliance with standards. Based on partner contributions, a Tool Vocabulary was compiled, which served as the basis for creating a Tool Ontology that systematically represents tools and their metadata.

- Implementation of Ontology Manager and Semantic Framework

Vicomtech developed the Ontology Manager, a service for managing ontologies and semantic functions. The PROVEN Ontology Manager (POM) is a backend web application that provides semantic services for ontology-based data management, validation, and enrichment.

The technical work related to Task 4.2, which addresses data fusion, semantic compression, and scenario representation for complex and extended scenarios, is described in detail in a dedicated chapter. An overview of the Task 4.2 contributions is provided in the chapter 3.4 Overview of Partner Contributions to Detection, Tracking, Fusion, and Scenario Representation, where partner-specific methods and implementations are presented in context.

3.2 Relation to other SYNERGIES Activities

Tasks 4.1 and 4.2 are closely integrated into the overall SYNERGIES architecture and jointly contribute to interoperability, semantic consistency, and efficient handling of complex data across multiple work packages. Task 4.1 provides the semantic foundations for tool and data interoperability, while Task 4.2 builds on these foundations by addressing data fusion and semantic compression for complex and extended scenarios. Their combined outputs support

consistent data representation, tool integration, and reuse across the project.

Figure 1 Work package relations

The design of the semantic framework, ontologies, and tool specifications in Task 4.1 was driven by requirements defined in WP2, ensuring alignment with project-wide conventions for data formats, metadata, and interoperability. In particular, Task 2.3 provided requirements for ontology usage and semantic descriptions. WP3 supplied raw and processed data that informed the development of the tool vocabulary and semantic integration concepts. In addition, data journeys provided by WP3 were used to identify existing tools across partners and to determine where further tool development was needed within WP4. The harmonization activities in Task 4.1, in turn, support WP3 by enabling consistent representation of data across different processing tools.

Task 4.2 extends this work by focusing on data fusion and semantic compression for scenarios involving dense spatio-temporal information and multiple interacting elements. The ontologies, vocabularies, and structured tool descriptions developed in Task 4.1 form the semantic basis for combining heterogeneous data sources and applying abstraction mechanisms in Task 4.2. This supports more efficient representation, storage, and replay of scenario data, while maintaining semantic clarity and consistency for further processing and simulation.

The tools developed in WP4 will be integrated into the SYNERGIES platform delivered by WP7, enabling automated reasoning and interoperability between marketplace tools. WP8 relies on this framework for traceability and semantic consistency, which are essential for evaluating platform performance and compliance. Finally, WP9 benefits from the transparency and explainability provided by semantic interoperability and structured tool descriptions, fostering trust and adoption among stakeholders.

3.3 Data formats

One of the main goals of the Synergies project is the development of tools to derive scenarios from data and to provide a platform to share such tools. In order for different tools from different organizations to interface with each other harmonization is required. To make this harmonization possible data formats are required.

In this context, data format refers to the internal structure or specification of the information stored within a file. The file format (e.g., JSON or XML) provides the underlying container, and the data format defines how the information is organized inside that container. Using established file formats helps ensure the content is interpretable by both computer systems and human users.

The data formats developed within this task have to allow for the specification of all information needed to derive scenarios that can be stored in associated scenario databases and then be used within the safety assurance process of CCAM vehicles. This entails the ground truth information captured by recordings of naturalistic traffic or driving simulators.

This data conforms to a data model or ontology that defines what is contained within the data and what relationship exist between different elements of the data. Based on this model a specification can then be provided to map the content to a file format for use, storage and exchange.

Figure 2 Process steps for the generation of Scenario Source Data

3.3.1 Requirements on Scenario Source Data

In the context of SYNERGIES, Scenario Source Data (SSD) corresponds to the data that is considered the basis for scenario identification and extraction. Such data can stem from multiple sources: in-traffic-vehicle data collection, fixed or mobile (e.g., drones) roadside observations, dynamic accident reconstruction, but also generative AI, traffic simulation.

The requirements for the SSD can be grouped into harmonization, tooling, traceability, content, quality exchange and metadata (see SYNERGIES Deliverable D2.2, Section 6.2) [2]:

- **Harmonization** requirements will focus on a standardized framework that ensures consistency and compatibility across the various data sources.
- **Tooling** requirements will emphasize the development of software and applications that facilitate the collection, processing, and analysis of SSD efficiently.
- **Traceability** requirements will ensure that all data points can be tracked back to their original sources, maintaining transparency and accountability throughout the process.

- **Content** requirements will specify the types of information that must be included in the SSD to support effective scenario identification and extraction.
- **Quality** requirements will outline criteria that data must meet to be considered reliable and valid for use.
- **Exchange** requirements will focus on defining how SSD can be shared between different stakeholders while ensuring security and integrity of the data.
- **Metadata** requirements will dictate what descriptive information should accompany the SSD to provide context, origin, and relevance of the data collected.

In summary, these requirements indicate that Scenario Source Data must facilitate seamless interoperability between various data collection and generation methods on the one side, and various scenario generation and extraction techniques, on the other side. Importantly, Scenario Source Data should be independent of its original source — meaning that its content should not rely on where it originated, such as the specific data collection device, generation tool, or processing pipeline. This key characteristic sets Scenario Source Data apart from Raw Data.

As previously noted, Scenario Source Data must be capable of representing information gathered from both static viewpoints (such as accident sites, drone footage, or roadside observations) and dynamic viewpoints, where data is collected from a moving vehicle navigating through traffic.

Furthermore, Scenario Source Data should remain neutral with respect to its intended use case. It must not embed assumptions regarding its interpretation during scenario identification and definition, nor should it be a form of highly abstracted or "semantically compressed" data. Instead, Scenario Source Data should faithfully represent reality as it is — capturing the nature, state, and geometry of relevant objects (including infrastructure and traffic participants), along with how these attributes evolve over time.

Within the SYNERGIES project, the OMEGA-PRIME format was designed to address those requirements and adequately represent and exchange Scenario Source Data. This format organizes data as a sequence of time-stamped observations detailing the properties, states, and kinematics of dynamic traffic elements (i.e., traffic participants) and environmental conditions (such as precipitation, illumination, and visibility). Coupled with a comprehensive map describing all relevant infrastructure attributes, OMEGA-PRIME aligns perfectly with the needs of Scenario Source Data.

3.3.2 OMEGA-PRIME Specification

Before developing OMEGA-PRIME, formats (and corresponding data models) used by participating partners were analysed and compared. These included formats developed to represent "fixed point reference" data, such as OMEGA from IKA and PCM from VUFO and "Moving point reference" such as L3PIlot CDF, Hi-Drive CDF, and ADSCENE's input data model and data format.

While all of those adequately addressed the needs of their respective designers and users, they presented significant differences:

- "Fixed point reference" formats implemented:
 - No real 'particular' vehicle (ego): every traffic participant's type, geometry & movement is described the same way,

- Vehicle coordinates in an absolute/fixed-point reference,
- A description of the infrastructure as a list of objects of different types, their shape/geometry being described in the same fixed reference.
- "Moving point reference" formats implemented:
 - A very particular vehicle: the 'ego' vehicle, that corresponded to the vehicle used to collect data, and everything is described from its own vantage point,
 - Other actors' coordinates representation in relation to the ego vehicle,
 - Infrastructure description as a combination of:
 - "General" context information for each successive location of the ego vehicle, evolving over time (e.g. number of lanes, speed limit),
 - Specific objects (e.g. traffic signs) derived from embedded perception, described in the same moving reference,

Figure 3 OMEGA-PRIME file structure

Additionally, while those formats mostly relied on standards such as HDF5 for the serialisation into a file, the actual data models they implemented (list of attributes, their names, types, enumerations etc.) were generally not relying on industry standards, and reflected the possibilities and constraints of the data collection pipeline that was associated with their creation.

OMEGA-PRIME was therefore designed to address those shortcomings and define a data model and format that can represent Scenario Source Data in a way that:

- Relies on existing standards, for which tooling already exists,
- Facilitates ultimate use of the data in simulation,
- Is entirely agnostic in terms of data origin,
- Represents infrastructure characteristics and traffic participants' type, trajectories, and state as they are, without further interpretation.

It relies on the following standards:

- ASAM OpenDrive v1.8.1 [3] for the infrastructure representation,
- ASAM OSI v3.7.0 GroundTruth messages [4] for moving elements,
- MCAP [5] for the container file format.

Two approaches exist within OMEGA-PRIME to associate map data with a continuous recording of traffic observations:

- The OpenDrive can directly be encapsulated into the MCAP file,
- Or, to avoid data duplication for successive recordings covering the same area and facilitate map maintenance, an external OpenDrive file can be referenced to, from a *map_reference* OSI Ground Truth message.

Additionally, since not all information that can be represented in the aforementioned standards is necessary for Scenario Source Data, and since those standards don't specify or enforce constraints on measures' precision, the OMEGA-PRIME specification also lists the fields that are necessary, and the minimum precision for each of them.

The full specification of the OMEGA-PRIME format as well as tools to facilitate its use in Python have been published in Open Source: GitHub - Omega-Prime: Data Model, Data Format and Python Library for Ground Truth Traffic Data [6].

3.4 Semantic framework

Building on the data format harmonization and tool investigations described in the previous sections, the Semantic Framework provides the formalized representation of tools, data formats, and workflow elements required within the SYNERGIES project. It captures the concepts and relationships identified in partner Data Journeys, organizes them into a shared Tool Vocabulary, and encodes them in a machine-readable Tool Ontology.

The Semantic Framework encompasses:

- **Tool vocabulary:** A harmonized set of terms derived from partner contributions to standardize tool concepts.
- **Tool Specification Template:** A structured metadata format for describing software tools consistently across partners.
- **Taxonomies and Standards:** Reference models and ontologies used to align terms with established definitions.
- **Tool Ontology:** A formal, OWL-based representation of tools, data converters and workflow steps, supporting automated reasoning, integration, and discoverability.
- **Extended Ontology Vocabulary:** Additional terms to capture AI-specific concepts not addressed by existing taxonomies or standards supporting the ontology used to represent the stored data.
- **Ontology Manager Tool:** A backend service providing ontology management and semantic queries.

The following subsections detail the design, construction, and implementation of these components, demonstrating how the framework consolidates partner contributions into a unified semantic asset for scenario development, tool integration and workflow interoperability.

3.4.1 Data journeys and tools

The first step in harmonizing information about the various tools used in the project was the definition of data journeys. Data journeys describe how different partners within the Synergies project initially capture data and the subsequent steps taken to process, label, and further handle that data. A set of data journeys has been defined within WP3.

These data journeys typically begin with data capture using sensor technologies such as cameras, radar, or lidar. Additional data sources may include map data or weather information. Sensors may be deployed in different ways, for example on roadside infrastructure, vehicles, or drones. The resulting raw data is then processed using a range of tools that may filter, fuse, or annotate the data, among other functions. The final step is the structuring of the processed data into one of the previously defined data formats, like the Scenario Source Data format or OmegaPrime.

Figure 4 Data Collection Journey AVL

The purpose of defining these data journeys is to identify the tools required at each stage, determine whether they already exist, can be provided by project partners, or need to be developed. This section of the deliverable aims to establish a common vocabulary and ontology for these tools, enabling harmonization across project stakeholders and fostering a shared understanding of the tools involved in the scenario data creation process. This common foundation also supports the integration of such tools into the Synergies Marketplace.

3.4.1.1 Tool vocabulary

A key observation that emerged from the collection of data journeys (0) from project partners within Synergies, was that inconsistent terminology was used throughout different organisations. The need to align terminology in the project was identified as a logical next step within the work package. A tool vocabulary was developed to align understanding of the terminology being used in the project regarding tools. This step is a precursor to ontology creation and provides the semantic understanding for an ontology to be designed. Tool specifications became available from partners planning to contribute tools to the Synergies platform, allowing for a relevant, partner sourced vocabulary to be established. Some definitions gave rise to identical definitions being used for different terminology, this was a key outcome of the task, to align definitions and arrive at a common understanding of key terms for tools within the project.

The tool vocabulary was developed iteratively, the initial contents came from the partners data journeys as described above (3.4.1) and were updated with the outcomes of the 'tool specification template', as they were completed by the partners who planned tool development within the project (as detailed in 3.4.1.2). The vocabulary is captured as an excel spreadsheet, the fields of which are detailed in the excerpt below. The vocabulary captures the term used in the specification template/data journey, the definition of the term, an indication of which partners data journey the term came from, and the taxonomy that the term is related to (detailed in 3.44). When consolidating terms and preparing them as the tool ontology, additional columns were added to the vocabulary to capture inheritance as superclass (parent term) and subclass (child term).

The vocabulary is maintained under the stewardship of the Work Package 4 team, who act as the central point of contact for any proposed additions or updates from other work packages. The vocabulary is centrally hosted within the project repository, ensuring accessibility across all work packages. Term conflicts and definition ambiguities were resolved through collaborative discussion with the relevant contributing partners, ensuring that agreed definitions reflect a consensus across the stakeholders most directly affected by their adoption. As the project evolves and further tool specifications are contributed to the Synergies platform, the vocabulary is designed to accommodate new terms through the same iterative, partner-driven process by which it was initially constructed, with updates coordinated through the Work Package 4 leads to maintain consistency with the established ontology.

Table 1 Tool vocabulary

#	Term name	Term definition	Superclass (parent)	Subclass (child)	Data Journey	Related Taxonomy
1	2D Object Detection	A computer vision task that identifies and localizes objects in 2D images using bounding boxes. The output includes object classes (e.g., car, pedestrian) and their 2D coordinates in the image plane.	Object Detection	Lane Detection	VICOM	Fusion & Perception taxonomies
2	2D Object Tracking	A process that links detected objects across frames in a video or image sequence, maintaining consistent object IDs over time in 2D space.	Object Tracking		VICOM	Fusion & Perception taxonomies
...

3.4.1.2 Tool specification template

The Tool Specification Template provides a structured way to describe software tools within the semantic framework. Its purpose is not to exhaustively enumerate all possible values for each field but to outline key metadata that can be used to describe a tool consistently across partners. This will allow to have a common metadata format for all the tools built in WP4. This metadata will be used in the tool marketplace to identify compatible tools for tool pipelines or to easily filter tools in the marketplace. The tool specification template can be defined as a JSON file with the following key/value pairs:

Table 2 Tool specification template

Key	Value	
<i>Tool ID</i>	ID to be assigned by Tool Marketplace, so this is a Unique Identifier of the tool. Can be a DOI, or other UUID format.	
<i>Tool Name</i>	Name assigned to the tool.	
<i>Tags</i>	Keywords selected from the Tool Vocabulary	
<i>Execution Framework</i>	Specifies the environment or system in which the tool operates (e.g., standalone application, command-line interface, web service, script, framework, etc.)	
<i>Operating System</i>	Target operating system where the tool can be executed.	
<i>ODD</i>	Specific Operational Design Domain this tool applies to. Specify N/A if not relevant.	
<i>Partner</i>	Partner responsible of the development of the tool.	
<i>Readiness level</i>	Indicator or maturity of the tool: Concept / Early Prototype, Alpha, Beta, Production Ready, Validated in Pilots	
<i>Release Date</i>	Last-release date, publication date, or the relevant date (e.g., date of package preparation).	
<i>Inputs</i>	Describes the data or information required by the tool to perform its function.	Format Details the specific structure or type of the input data (e.g., CSV file, JSON object, pointcloud format, image format, etc.).
		Other Other properties considered by the ontology for the input data (e.g., data frequency, data source, etc.)
<i>Outputs</i>	Describes the results or information generated by the tool after processing the inputs.	Format Details the specific structure or type of the output data (e.g., ASAM OSI, ASAM OpenLABEL, SSD file, graphical visualization, etc.).

	Other	Other properties considered by the ontology for the output data (e.g., data frequency, etc.)
<i>Description</i>	Description of what the tool is designed for.	
<i>Available Tool Marketplace</i>	Indexed in the SYNERGIES Tool Marketplace (true/false).	
<i>WP</i>	Related Work Package in SYNERGIES. If several, add several. If none, specify N/A	
<i>Task</i>	Related Task in SYNERGIES. If several, add several. If none, specify N/A	
<i>Link</i>	Link to repository, URI of API, package download webpage or equivalent resource	
<i>License Type</i>	If applicable, outlines any licensing terms, usage limitations, or access requirements associated with the tool.	
<i>Contact / Maintainer</i>	Specifies the person or team responsible for the tool's development, maintenance, and support. This provides a point of contact for questions, bug reports, and feature requests.	
<i>Version</i>	Indicates the current version of the tool.	
<i>Comments</i>	Free comments by developer/owner	
<i>Tool documentation template</i>	Link to the Tool documentation template, containing detailed information about the tool for integration into platform.	

An example of a tool specification used for pedestrian detection on images in the RTMaps Framework can be seen here:

Table 3 Tool specification example

Key	Value
<i>Tool ID</i>	uuid (set by the platform)
<i>Tool Name</i>	Pedestrian Detector
<i>Tags</i>	"Object Detection", "2D Object Detection", "AI-based Object Detection"

<i>Execution Framework</i>	RTMaps		
<i>Operating System</i>	Linux		
<i>ODD</i>	Urban, Highway		
<i>Partner</i>	Vicomtech		
<i>Readiness level</i>	Alpha		
<i>Release Date</i>	14/11/2025		
<i>Inputs</i>	Image	Format	RTMaps Image
		Frequency	10Hz
		Data source	Exterior vehicle cameras.
<i>Outputs</i>	[2D BBOX, 2D Pose]	Format	ASAM OSI
<i>Description</i>	A sample tool for demonstration purposes.		
<i>Available Tool Marketplace</i>	False		
<i>WP</i>	WP4		
<i>Task</i>	T4.4		
<i>Link</i>	www.example.com		
<i>License Type</i>	MIT		
<i>Contact / Maintainer</i>	test_contact@test.com		
<i>Version</i>	0.1		
<i>Comments</i>	Example tool specification template. This is not a real tool.		

Corresponding JSON file

```

1.  1. {
2.    "tool_id": "TBD",
3.    "tool_name": "Pedestrian Detector",
4.    "description": "A sample tool for demonstration purposes.",
5.    "tags": [
6.      "Object Detection",
7.      "2D Object Detection",
8.      "AI-based Object Detection"
9.    ],
10.   "inputs": [
11.     {
12.       "name": "Image",
13.       "format_type": "RTMaps Image",
14.       "other_properties": {
15.         "frequency": "10Hz",
16.         "dataSource": "Exterior vehicle cameras"
17.       }
18.     }
19.   ],
20.   "outputs": [
21.     {
22.       "name": "2D BBOX",
23.       "format_type": "ASAM OSI",
24.       "other_properties": {}
25.     },
26.     {
27.       "name": "2D Pose",
28.       "format_type": "ASAM OSI",
29.       "other_properties": {}
30.     }
31.   ],
32.   "execution_framework": [
33.     "RTMaps"
34.   ],
35.   "operating_system": [
36.     "Linux"
37.   ],
38.   "odd": "Urban",
39.   "partner": "Vicomtech",
40.   "readiness_level": "Alpha",
41.   "release_date": "14/11/2025",
42.   "version": "0.1",
43.   "tool_marketplace": false,
44.   "license_type": "MIT",
45.   "wp": [
46.     "WP4"
47.   ],
48.   "task": [
49.     "T4.4"
50.   ],
51.   "link": "www.example.com",
52.   "contact": [
53.     "test\_contact@test.com"
54.   ],
55.   "comments": "Example tool specification template. This is not a real tool."
56. }
57.

```

In addition to the semantic tooling developed in WP4, the SYNERGIES project defines a Tool Documentation Template within Task 7.1 to support the documentation and presentation of tools at the platform level. This template is intended primarily for human-oriented use cases, complementing the machine-readable specifications developed in Task 4.1.

While the Tool Documentation Template targets front-end presentation and user interaction, it is complemented by the Tool Specification Template developed in Task 4.1, which provides a structured, machine-readable description of tools for interoperability and pipeline composition.

Together, these templates ensure that tools within SYNERGIES are both well documented for human users and formally described for system-level integration, addressing different but complementary requirements within the overall architecture.

3.4.2 Ontology definition

Using an ontology for knowledge representation provides a formal, machine-interpretable structure that captures not only the terms in a domain but also the relationships, constraints, and logic that govern how those terms interact. This enables richer reasoning, interoperability between systems, and consistent interpretation across organisations and tools - capabilities that simple vocabularies or taxonomies cannot fully provide. A tool like Protégé [7] supports this process by allowing you to map existing data representations (e.g., vocabularies, glossaries, taxonomies, spreadsheets) and then incrementally enrich them with semantic structure: defining classes, properties, individuals, constraints, and axioms.

It was determined that dedicated ontologies should be developed to represent both the scenario-level concepts and the terminology associated with the platform's toolchain. This ensures that the data-focused notions essential to the platform are modelled in a clear, structured, and interoperable way, allowing them to be referenced consistently across all components as the system grows. The following work in this work package would focus on the tool ontology, whereas the scenario related concepts will be covered within work package 5.

The ontology definition activities were guided by requirements identified in Task 2.3, which define key expectations for semantic modelling within SYNERGIES. These requirements specify that ontologies must be provided in standardised, open formats (e.g. OWL with RDF/Turtle serialisation) to ensure accessibility and reuse. They further require a unified semantic representation of scenario elements, built where possible on established ontologies and standards, to support consistency across heterogeneous data sources. Additional requirements address modularity and scalability, enabling different work packages to extend relevant parts of the ontology independently, as well as support for multiple levels of abstraction and ontology-based inference to relate abstract scenarios to more concrete instantiations. These requirements directly informed the scope, structure, and design principles applied to the ontologies developed in this work package.

3.4.3 Ontology catalogue for Scenario generation

Ontologies can be used to define the relationship between different concepts in a domain. In the domain of driving scenarios, we can broadly divide ontologies into those defining an Operational Design Domain (ODD) more broadly and those defining specific driving scenarios.

OpenODD

The OpenODD standard is a framework for describing ODDs for automated driving systems developed within the ASAM family [8]. The first version has been released as of April 2025. The standard fulfils the need for a possibility to represent the ODD in simulations in a machine-readable form. This helps to create a boundry for testing within a scenario-based testing framework. OpenODD includes a taxonomy of different concepts needed to model the ODD, as well as rules to include and exclude certain conditions from the ODD. A mapping exists to map the ontology to the OpenSCENARIO DSL standard, as well as to a YAML description.

OpenXOntology

The ASAM OpenXOntology is an attempt to provide a harmonized description of core concepts from a range of different ASAM standards [9]. While not finished, a first version of the ontology in OWL format, as well as an accompanying description is available. The OpenXOntology follows a layered approach, with a core ontology, domain ontology and multiple application ontologies to cover different areas like scenarios or ODDs. The core ontology covers the basics, such as the definition for objects, events, and activities, while the domain ontology covers specific concepts related to traffic.

OpenLABEL

ASAM OpenLABEL is a standard meant for annotation of scenarios [10]. Different categorizations for annotations of objects and scenarios by different stakeholders are a problem for AD system development, since it hinders sharing of data, introduces problems in communications and increases the probability for errors. The OpenLABEL standard includes an ontology that covers both static and dynamic scenario content. Especially the dynamic content described in the ontology is limited in scope. Additionally, a JSON format exists to enable the representation of labels.

SUNRISE Ontology

Within the SUNRISE project, an ontology has been created to cover scenario content. This ontology is based on taxonomies described in the ISO 34503 and ISO 34504 norms and adds relationships between the elements within these norms, as well as definitions for possible attributes and instances. Detailed information on the ontology is available in the SUNRISE project deliverable D5.2 [11].

Gaia-X Ontology

Gaia-X provides definitions for the exchange of simulation assets. These assets can be of different types, covering needs for simulation such as maps or scenarios. For the description of scenarios, an ontology exists, to enable definition of metadata for the scenarios.

OpenSCENARIO and OpenDRIVE

Formats for the description of scenario content, such as the standards of OpenSCENARIO and OpenDRIVE contain specifications that define available elements and their relation. These are however not consistent with commonly used formats for ontology description but are instead available as xml schema files.

3.4.4 Taxonomies

Taxonomies provide structured, hierarchical representations of domain knowledge, allowing complex concepts to be defined, related, and reused in a consistent and machine-interpretable way. In the context of this project, establishing a clear taxonomy early on ensures that the terminology used across tools, scenarios, and analysis pipelines is aligned with existing industry practice and avoids unnecessary reinvention. For this reason, we first examined established taxonomies to determine whether the terms in our tool vocabulary were already formally defined elsewhere, and to ensure that our work builds on recognised foundations rather than creating isolated definitions. There was no singular existing taxonomy which contained all terms that had been identified in the tool vocabulary. There was a large amount of term coverage when the taxonomies from 5 different sources were considered.

For terms directly related to ADS and ADAS functionalities the taxonomies for reference are; *SAE J3016 – Taxonomy and Definitions for Driving Automation Systems Terminology [12]*, *PAS 1883: Operational Design Domain (ODD) taxonomy for an automated driving system (ADS) – Specification*

[13] *liError! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.* and ISO 34503: Road Vehicles – Test scenarios for automated driving systems – Specification for operational design domain [14]. SAE J3016 provides a standardized taxonomy and detailed definitions for six levels of driving automation—from no automation (Level 0) to full automation (Level 5). Meanwhile, BSI PAS 1883 (UK) provides a concrete ODD taxonomy that is more detailed in terms of road types, traffic, weather etc., and ISO 34503 builds on that by specifying a hierarchical attribute taxonomy and a formal definition format for ODDs targeted especially at level-3/4 ADS.

For terms related to data and data handling, there are not any standardised taxonomies available, two reference taxonomies from the research community were used where applicable. One taxonomy covers terms related to fusion [15] and another taxonomy covers terms related to perception [16].

Scenario tagging class hierarchy

Figure 5 ASAM OpenLABEL scenario tagging class hierarchy and layered tagging model, illustrating the coverage of existing standards (OpenODD, OpenXOntology, BSI PAS 1883) and the boundaries of their term coverage at the application level

Whilst the five taxonomies above collectively provide substantial term coverage, understanding how they relate to one another is important for establishing where genuine gaps exist and where new elements are therefore necessary. Figure 3 illustrates the relationship between the ASAM OpenLABEL and OpenXOntology frameworks, which together form the most comprehensive application-level basis for scenario-related terminology in this domain. The tagging model shown organises terms into distinct layers: administrative metadata at the application level; ODD dynamic, environment, and scenery terms which are aligned with both OpenODD and OpenXOntology and mapped to BSI PAS 1883; and Road User and Behaviour terms which map directly to OpenXOntology. This makes clear that whilst existing standards provide strong coverage of ODD and behaviour-related terms, the administrative and application-level metadata space, as well as terms specific to data handling, fusion, and perception, falls outside their scope. It is precisely these gaps that motivate the introduction of tool ontology elements in the following section, where a unified ontology is developed to capture the full vocabulary of terms identified across the tools proposed in this project.

3.4.5 Tool Ontology

The development of the Tool Ontology builds upon the results of the data-journey analysis and the tool vocabulary. The partner-specific data journeys provided a detailed picture of how scenario data is captured, processed, annotated, transformed, and prepared for use within SYNERGIES. These descriptions enabled the identification of tools required at each stage of the workflow and exposed inconsistencies in terminology across partners.

To address this, a harmonised tool vocabulary was developed as a precursor to formal ontology creation. It consolidated terms originating from partner data journeys and the tool specification templates, aligning definitions and resolving overlaps. The resulting spreadsheet—containing term names, definitions, partner origins, related taxonomies, and superclass/subclass relationships—served as the semantic foundation upon which the Tool Ontology was constructed.

The SYNERGIES Tool Ontology formalizes the representation of data formats, data converters, and software tools used in autonomous driving scenario development. It supports automated reasoning, tool discovery, and data conversion workflows.

Key purposes of the ontology include:

1. Standardizing data formats and converters, enabling consistent interpretation and interoperability.
2. Providing rich metadata for tools, including license, version, maintainer programming language, operating system (OS), and repository information.
3. Supporting reproducibility and interoperability within SYNERGIES by documenting tool provenance, dependencies, and data transformations.

The Tool Vocabulary and Ontology together constitute a foundational semantic asset within the project. They provide a unified conceptual framework for describing, comparing, and integrating the diverse tools and processes used by partners. This ensures that the ontology is grounded in real operational practices while enabling interoperability across heterogeneous systems and consistent integration into the SYNERGIES Marketplace.

3.4.5.1 Ontology Scope

- **Domain:** Autonomous driving, scenario data management, tool metadata.
- **Entities modelled:**
 - **Data formats:** Raw, annotated, and standardized formats (e.g., JSON, MCAP, SSD, ROS messages).
 - **Data converters:** Software components that transform data between formats (e.g., OSMODRConverter, ROS to SSD Converter).
 - **Software tools and their metadata:** License, version, maintainer, programming language, operating system.
- **Intended Users:** Developers, data engineers, researchers, workflow designers, and project managers.

3.4.5.2 Construction Process

The ontology was developed following a structured methodology and implemented using the Protégé [7] ontology editor, ensuring compliance with OWL standards [17].

1. **Extraction of Terms from Partner Data Journeys:** Terms, concepts, data formats, and tools were systematically identified from the detailed descriptions of partner data

- journeys and tool specifications. This provided a raw, heterogeneous list of candidate concepts.
2. **Term Consolidation and Definition:** The preliminary list was reviewed to remove duplicates and resolve naming inconsistencies. Formal definitions were produced for all terms, drawing on project documentation and external standards (e.g., SAE J3016, ISO 34503). Each term was also mapped to relevant taxonomies (e.g., SAE J3259, PAS 1883), ensuring alignment with international terminology.
 3. **Classification and Ontological Modelling:** Terms were mapped to structural dependencies, including class–subclass hierarchies and part-of relations. This step introduced essential superclasses such as **Detection Tool**, **Conversion Tool**, and **Data Workflow Process** to support a coherent and modular structure.
 4. **RDF/OWL Modelling and Alignment:** The curated concepts were formally encoded in RDF/OWL. This formalisation supports machine-readable data interoperability, integration into knowledge graphs, and enables validation and reasoning functionalities (e.g., SPARQL inference) for managing tool chains and workflows.

The resulting hierarchy captures both shared aspects across partners and specialized elements relevant to individual data journeys. Hence, the resulting Tool Ontology provides a harmonised and semantically coherent representation of tools, data formats, and workflow steps. It enhances interoperability between partners, supports consistent documentation, and fosters clearer communication across development teams. The explicit modelling of tool relations, versions, and data transformations strengthens reproducibility and transparency in workflow execution. The ontology also provides a reusable semantic layer for integration with other SYNERGIES assets—such as metadata catalogues, knowledge graphs, and automated reasoning services—improving tool discoverability and the management of data-processing pipelines.

3.4.5.3 Modeling Rationale and Design Patterns

The architectural design of the SYNERGIES Tool Ontology adopts a modular and federated ontology design pattern. The knowledge representation is organized around the intersection of two distinct namespaces with separated domain responsibilities:

- **Domain-Specific Functional Layer (prefix synergies or tool-vocabulary):** Governs the operational vocabulary tied to autonomous driving system (ADS) workflows, data acquisition, and core Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) processes. High-level classes within this scope, such as `DrivingEnvironmentMonitoring`, `DataConverter`, `DataFormat`, are anchored to established automotive industry definitions like the SAE J3016 functional standard.
- **Abstract Software Metadata Layer (prefix ontology):** Manages the generic software engineering metadata lifecycle. It provides an abstract framework to describe software artifacts uniformly using concepts such as `Tool`, `Version`, `Dependency` and `License`.

This separation of namespaces minimizes semantic coupling while maximizing cross-domain reusability. It allows functional modules (e.g., a specific `DataConverter`) to interact dynamically with software management attributes (e.g., its related code `Repository`) without causing structural pollution within the main ontology tree.

3.4.5.3.1 Pipeline Composition and Constraint Patterns

To directly address the automated orchestration and discovery needs of the SYNERGIES Marketplace platform, specific semantic design choices and formal constraints were enforced at the property level:

- The Input-Output Contract Pattern: The object properties `hasInputDataFormat` and `hasOutputDataFormat` explicitly declare `DataConverter` as their domain and `DataFormat` as their range. This formal restriction establishes a machine-readable semantic contract for data pipelines. Consequently, reasoners can programmatically infer pipeline compatibility validating whether the output format of a preceding tool matches the input expectations of a subsequent one.
- Cardinality and Functional Property Constraints: To maintain strict data integrity regarding software descriptions, critical metadata relations such as `hasCurrentVersion`, `hasLicense`, and `hasName` are defined as `owl:FunctionalProperty` types. This constraint guarantees that any given individual instance of a `Tool` can evaluate to exactly one unique name, one active license, and one primary production version string at any single point in time, mitigating ambiguity during SPARQL query executions.
- AI Classification via Polymorphic Domains: The datatype property `isAIbased` utilizes an `owl:unionOf` constructor to bind its domain to a logical collection of classes: `DataAnnotation`, `ObjectClassification`, `ObjectDetection` and `ObjectTracking`. This avoids property duplication across the tree and allows the reasoner to enforce a clean boolean categorization, distinguishing deep learning or machine learning-driven components from traditional rule-based algorithms.

3.4.5.4 Tool Ontology Structure

The SYNERGIES Tool Ontology formalizes the representation of various entities within the scenario data creation process, including Data formats, Data converters, and Software tools. Its structure is implemented in OWL and derived from the harmonized Tool Vocabulary and the functional steps identified in the Data Journeys.

The structure is built around a defined class hierarchy and a set of properties that describe the relationships and metadata of the entities.

3.4.5.4.1 Key Classes and Hierarchy

The ontology is partitioned into two main areas: **Functional Classes** (describing data flow and operations) and **Metadata Classes** (describing tool characteristics).

1) Functional and Data Flow Classes

These classes model the tools and data involved in the scenario creation workflow, inheriting from the high-level classes **Data** and **DataWorkflow**:

Figure 6 Class hierarchy of the SYNERGIES Tool Ontology.

- **Data:** The foundational class for all data elements.
 - **DataFormat:** Represents specific data structures (e.g., SSD, MCAP, OpenDRIVE).
 - **ScenarioData:** High-level data types used in scenarios.
 - **SceneContext:** Contextual information like maps and ODDs.
 - **MapModeling:** Tools and data related to map management (e.g., HDMap, OpenDriveMapFilesProvider).
 - **DrivingEnvironmentMonitoring:** Represents core perception functions.
 - **ObjectDetection** (e.g., 2DObjectDetection, 3DObjectDetection).
 - **ObjectTracking** (e.g., 2DObjectTracking, 3DObjectTracking).
 - **SLAM:** Simultaneous Localization and Mapping.
 - **DataFusion:** Processes for combining data.
 - **SensorFusion** (e.g., PointCloudFusion, MultiCameraObjectFusion).
 - **DataWorkflow:** High-level process steps.

- **DataPreprocessing** (e.g., Anonimization, Synchronization).
- **DataAnnotation** (e.g., ManualDataAnnotation).
- **DataConverter**: A specific tool type for translating data between formats (e.g., ROStoSSDConverter).
- **LabellingTool**: Software interface for data annotation (e.g., WebLABEL).
- **DataVisualization**: Components for displaying data (e.g., ScenarioViewer).

2) Tool Metadata Classes

These classes are used to describe the **Tool** class and its characteristics:

Figure 7 Subclass hierarchy of Metadata in the SYNERGIES Tool Ontology.

- **Tool**: The root class for all software components. It is constrained to always have a **Maintainer** and a **Version**.
- **Metadatum**: The abstract superclass for descriptive information. Subclasses include:
 - **Version**: Details of the tool's iteration.
 - **License**: Licensing information (e.g., LicenseMIT).
 - **Maintainer**: The entity responsible for the tool.
 - **ProgrammingLanguage**: The implementation language (e.g., Python).
 - **OperatingSystem**: The environment the tool runs on (e.g., Linux).

3) Object Properties and Relations

The relationships between classes are modelled using Object Properties, which are critical for describing the toolchain and dependencies:

Figure 8 Object properties of the SYNERGIES Tool ontology.

Table 4 Object properties definition.

Property name	Domain (From Class)	Range (To Class)	Description
hasInputDataFormat	DataConverter	DataFormat	Specifies the exact format or protocol consumed by the converter.
hasOutputDataFormat	DataConverter	DataFormat	Specifies the exact format or protocol produced by the converter.
dependsOn	Tool	Dependency	Models external software/library dependencies.
ImplementedIn	Tool	ProgrammingLanguage	Links the tool to the language used for its implementation.
runsOnOS	Tool	OperatingSystem	Specifies the compatible operating system.
hasLicense	Tool	License	Links the tool to its licensing terms.

hasRepository	Tool	Repository	Provides the link to the tool's source code repository.
---------------	------	------------	---

4) Data Properties

These properties link functional classes to literal data values:

Figure 9 Data properties of the SYNERGIES Tool ontology.

Table 5 Data properties definition

Property name	Domain (From Class)	Range (To Data Type)	Description
isAIbased	Union of Classes: Detection/Tracking/Annotation	Boolean	Indicates whether the core function relies on Machine Learning or Deep Learning models.
hasName	Tool	String	The official name of the tool.
hasVersionNumber	Version	String	The specific version string (e.g., "1.2.0").

This explicit modelling of tool relations, metadata, and data transformations ensures interoperability, supports consistent documentation, and facilitates the integration of tools into the SYNERGIES Marketplace.

3.4.5.4.2 Individuals and Instances

While the classes and properties define the *structure* of the domain, the Individuals (or Instances) provide concrete examples of the data formats, tools, and metadata used within the project. These instances were primarily drawn from the Tool Specification Template and the defined Data Journeys.

1) Data Formats

These individuals are **instances** of the `DataFormat` class, representing the specific file types and communication protocols used at various stages of the data workflow.

Table 6 Data format class instances.

Individual	Type	Description
BinaryFile	DataFormat	Generic binary file format.
JSON	DataFormat	JSON Format.
MCAP	DataFormat	Message Container for Autonomous Perception; stores sequential sensor/log data.
OMEGAFormat	DataFormat	SYNERGIES-specific scenario source data container (based on ASAM OSI/OpenDRIVE within an MCAP container).
OpenDRIVE	DataFormat	Industry standard for road network geometry and logic.
OpenLABEL	DataFormat	Standard for annotating sensor data (objects, events, scenarios).
OpenStreetMap	DataFormat	Open-source geospatial data.
PCD	DataFormat	Point cloud data format.
ProtobufMessages	DataFormat	Protocol buffer messages.
ROSMessages	DataFormat	ROS framework communication messages.
SSD	DataFormat	Scenario Source Data model (traffic participants, environment, etc.).

2) Data Converters

These individuals are specific instances of the `DataConverter` class, illustrating how data is transformed between the defined formats to maintain interoperability along the data journey.

Table 7 Data Converter class instances.

Individual	Input	Output	Description
OSMODRConverter	OpenStreetMap	OpenDRIVE	Converts OSM data to OpenDRIVE.
OpenLABELandHDMapSSDConverter	OpenDRIVE, OpenLABEL	SSD	Combines annotated objects and HD maps into the Scenario Source Data (SSD) format.

ROStoSSDConverter	ROSMesssage	SSD	Converts ROS messages to SSD.
-------------------	-------------	-----	-------------------------------

3) Labelling Tool

For the `LabellingTool` class a unique individual has been defined.

Table 8 Labelling tool class instances.

Individual	Type	Description
WebLabel	LabellingTool	Is a web-based labelling tool used for annotating image, video, or 3D data directly in a browser. It supports collaborative annotation workflows, user roles, and integrates with cloud storage and automation services. It may include both manual and AI-assisted annotation features, making it useful in large-scale data labeling projects.

This explicit instantiation ensures that tools integrated into the SYNERGIES Marketplace are uniformly described, supporting both **discoverability** and **reproducibility** by clearly documenting their provenance and technical requirements.

3.4.6 Ontology Manager Tool

The PROVEN Ontology Manager (POM) is a web-based semantic service designed to enable ontology-driven data management and interoperability within the semantic framework. Developed by Vicomtech as part of the PROVEN® technology suite, the tool provides backend functionalities for Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems.

POM (version 1.0.0) acts as a semantic microservice that exposes ontology and reasoning functionalities through REST APIs. It enables external tools and applications to load and manage ontologies, execute semantic queries, validate data consistency, and perform semantic similarity computations using Natural Language Processing (NLP) models. By offering a uniform access layer to semantic resources, POM ensures machine-interpretable, interoperable, and ontology-compliant data handling across the PROVEN ecosystem.

3.4.6.1 Standards and Interoperability

POM is fully aligned with W3C Semantic Web standards, supporting RDF, OWL, and SPARQL 1.1 specifications for ontology representation and reasoning. It natively handles ontology file formats such as .ttl, .rdf, and .owl, ensuring compatibility with major semantic tools (e.g., Protégé, Apache Jena, RDF4J).

The RESTful API adheres to the OpenAPI (Swagger) standard, facilitating easy integration with other components in the PROVEN ecosystem and third-party systems. In addition, POM follows the ASAM OpenLABEL [9] data model conventions for representing Objects, Contexts, Actions, and Events, ensuring interoperability with labeling and annotation standards used in the CCAM domain.

3.4.6.2 Architecture

POM is built on a modular, containerized microservice architecture orchestrated via Docker Compose, which ensures consistent deployment, scalability, secure internal communication across local or remote environments and seamless integration within the Semantic Framework.

The architecture consists of three primary layers:

- **Semantic Storage Layer:** Powered by Ontotext GraphDB [18], this high-performance triplestore handles the persistent storage of ontologies and instance data while providing advanced SPARQL endpoints for querying and inference. A dedicated initialization container automatically provisions the repository during startup, mapping namespaces and prefixes without manual intervention.
- **Semantic Service Layer:** A Flask-based API serves as the central interface between external applications and the semantic storage. It encapsulates all complex logic required for repository lifecycle management, ontology exploration, instance creation, and semantic similarity computation using NLP models.
- **Documentation and Developer Interface:** An interactive API-Swagger portal is exposed to allow developers to seamlessly visualize, test, and integrate the system's endpoints into other applications.

Figure 10 Ontology Manager functional architecture

3.4.6.3 Functionalities

Rather than functioning merely as a static database, POM provides a comprehensive suite of functionalities that support the entire lifecycle of semantic data:

- **Repository and Ontology Management:** The system allows for the dynamic creation and deletion of isolated GraphDB repositories, ensuring flexible separation of ontologies across different projects or domains. It supports dynamic ontology integration, seamlessly ingesting structural updates as the framework evolves.
- **Ontology Exploration and Validation:** POM exposes the underlying semantic structure, enabling external services to traverse class hierarchies, retrieve object and datatype properties, and verify transitive subclass relationships. Dedicated functionalities exist to retrieve specific hierarchies governed by the ASAM OpenLABEL standard (e.g., *Objects*, *Contexts*, *Actions*, *Events*).
- **Instance Handling:** The API enables the programmatic population of the ontology, allowing external tools to insert and retrieve individual instances while automatically ensuring type consistency and valid property assignments.

- **AI-Assisted Semantic Matching:** To bridge the gap between human input and formal ontologies, POM incorporates an AI-based NLP Sentence Transformer. This enables the calculation of semantic similarity between textual inputs and ontology labels. Furthermore, it can validate structured data files against the ontology to guarantee that schemas and annotations comply strictly with the defined semantic model.

3.4.6.4 Integration and Use Cases

The POM module is conceived as the semantic backend of the PROVEN framework, supporting data fusion, labeling, and validation tools.

Two main integration scenarios are identified:

- A) **Labeling Tools (e.g., WebLabel [19]):** Provides a controlled vocabulary of ontology concepts (objects, actions, contexts, events) for consistent labeling and annotation and uses similarity matching to align user-defined labels with ontology terms.
- B) **Semantic Validation Tools:** Supports the verification of data and annotations against ontology structures, checking class hierarchies, domain/range consistency, and relation validity to ensure semantic integrity.

3.4.6.5 Ontology Extension with AI Model-Specific Attributes

The ontology functionalities specified in Section 3.4.6.3, while primarily applied to the construction of a tool ontology within this deliverable, are equally applicable to the development of ontologies supporting the storage of generated data (WP3) and scenario generation (WP5) concepts. The ontology developed for scenario generation concepts largely follows established taxonomies such as ISO 34503 and ontologies such as OpenXOntology as described in Section 3.4.3. These provide a robust structure for representing scenario-level concepts, including actors, environments, and scenery elements. However, when considering ontologies intended for the storage and annotation of generated data, these constructs prove insufficient.

This absence of a standardised ontology for generated data introduces a semantic gap, particularly for attributes that are critical to AI-based detection and perception pipelines. Such attributes are often available within perception and data generation systems but are not formalised within existing scenario taxonomies. As a result, they are typically omitted from scenario descriptions despite their direct influence on the performance and behaviour of AI models during testing and validation.

The attributes targeted by the ontology extension developed in this task are ultimately important for AI models used in detection, perception, and tracking. While these attributes may not always manifest explicitly in traditional scenario descriptions (and are therefore not covered by existing scenario ontologies), they remain an essential part of an accurate and reproducible scenario representation. Examples include parameters related to reflectivity, dimensionality, etc. which can influence how a System Under Test (SUT) performs in a generated scenario.

The ontology extension does not aim to represent all available parameters from the data generation stage. Instead, it focuses on those elements that must be explicitly captured during scenario generation, as they may influence AI model performance when the ADS is evaluated. In this sense, the extension operates at an intermediate semantic level between data generation outputs and scenario generation inputs.

The ontology extension provides semantic constructs for those terms and attributes from generated data that are relevant to scenario generation and ADS evaluation but are typically not included in scenario descriptions themselves. These influential attributes may emerge during scenario generation as what can be characterised as micro-parameters [19], although rarely included in scenario descriptions (of OpenX format), have a measurable impact on the detection and perception performance of the ADS.

By explicitly modelling these micro-parameters within the semantic framework, the ontology extension strengthens the link between generated data, scenarios generated, and testing of AI-driven ADS functions [20].

3.4.6.5.1 Steps for Ontology Extension with AI Model-Specific Attributes

The following steps describe the methodology adopted for the development of the ontology extension with AI model-specific attributes. In addition to documenting the approach taken in this task, they are intended to serve as guidance for future ontology extensions, for instance, those targeting AI model-specific attributes beyond perception-related ADS functions.

1. Existing Scenario-Related Ontology

The starting point for the ontology extension is the existing scenario ontology, developed within WP5, which covers core elements such as scenery elements (e.g. road network, surface conditions), dynamic agents (e.g. vehicles, pedestrians), and environmental conditions (e.g. weather, illumination). While this ontology provides a structured representation of what is present in a scenario, it misses certain data recorded during the data journeys and is excluded in what is represented semantically.

Several attributes that emerge during data generation are not carried forward into scenario representation. These missing aspects are those that have a direct influence on AI model performance, especially for detection, perception, and tracking tasks. As a result, reconstructed/generated scenarios may omit information that affects how the ADS perceives and responds to the scenario during testing.

The ontology extension therefore focuses exclusively on attributes that are relevant to AI-based detection, perception, and tracking, rather than attempting to exhaustively capture all generated data. This scoped approach ensures that only semantically meaningful attributes, those that influence ADS behaviour and performance, are formalised.

2. Expansion of length and breadth of elements

The first expansion step proceeds from the existing ontology structure and systematically extends it both in depth and scope. Beginning at established leaf nodes, additional attributes are introduced where perception-relevant detail is currently absent.

For example, if pedestrian is a leaf node in the dynamic agent hierarchy, the ontology is extended to include attributes such as:

- Dimensional representation (e.g. 2D rather than generally expected 3D),
- Physical appearance characteristics, including clothing type
- Clothing sub-attributes, such as colour, texture, and reflectivity
- Use of mobility aids (e.g. wheelchairs, crutches, walkers)
- Behavioural patterns associated with mobility aids, including speed variability and motion constraints

This expansion enables a richer semantic description of scenario elements that are critical to the perception stage, ensuring that subsequent ADS functions are influenced in a realistic and

consistent manner. As a result, these elements must be explicitly considered during scenario generation.

3. Clustering of attributes

To ensure structure and reusability across the ontology, newly introduced attributes are grouped into coherent attribute clusters. Typical clusters include:

- Physical properties
- Orientation
- Appearance and visual characteristics
- Material properties
- Motion constraints

Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs), for example, share a common underlying concept of *human*, meaning that the same sub-classes and physical properties apply across all VRU instances. However, behavioural properties differ between VRU types, such as pedestrians and cyclists, and must be modelled accordingly. Clustering supports consistent modelling across different object classes and enables reasoning and reuse across multiple scenario instances and data sources.

4. Identification of AI-Influential Attributes (Micro-Parameters)

From the expanded set of attributes, only those deemed AI-influential are retained as part of the ontology extension. These attributes, referred to as *micro-parameters*, are selected based on:

- Their known impact on state-of-the-art AI architectures used for detection, perception, and tracking,
- Insights from partner pipelines and data journeys
- Expert judgement regarding their influence on ADS performance

Attributes that do not demonstrably affect AI model behaviour are excluded to avoid unnecessary semantic complexity.

Figure 11 Snippet of ontology extension for Human showing sub-classes and properties on Protege

5. Naming and Hierarchical Alignment of Attributes

All retained attributes are named and structured in accordance with the class hierarchy and element management principles defined in earlier sections of this deliverable. Depending on their semantic role and reusability, some attribute clusters are modelled as properties, while others are introduced as sub-classes within the ontology. This design choice ensures consistency with the modelling approach adopted for the Tool Ontology and supports automated reasoning by the reasoner.

3.5 Overview of Partner Contributions to Detection, Tracking, Fusion, and Scenario Representation

This chapter provides an overview of the individual contributions of CEESAR, Vicomtech, and VIF to Task 4.2, reflecting the broad technical scope of the work on perception, fusion, and structured scenario representation for complex urban environments. The reported activities cover complementary components of the overall toolchain, including object detection and tracking, multi-source fusion, mapping and preprocessing, and scenario reconstruction and integration into higher-level generation workflows. In this context, Vicomtech has contributed a cuboid-based tracking framework and is extending its work toward cuboid fusion and 2D-to-3D projection methods, while CEESAR has focused on object tracking and the evaluation of detection algorithms using image and point cloud data, alongside mapping, geo-referencing, and preprocessing activities. VIF has primarily contributed to the coordination and technical integration of the scenario reconstruction functionality, with emphasis on validating the approach using recorded measurements and embedding it into the scenario generation tool. Taken together, these contributions support the conversion of heterogeneous urban scene data into structured, reusable representations suitable for simulation, validation, and scenario-based development.

3.5.1 CEESAR

CEESAR has developed a data collection platform and a processing pipeline to generate driving scenarios from open road driving, with a focus on urban environments.

Raw data from the sensors is processed to perform localization, detection, and tracking, in order to generate Omega-Prime files from the open road records. Algorithms identify interesting scenarios within these recordings. The relevant files are then used to enrich a database of driving scenarios.

Figure 12 Processing pipeline

3.5.1.1 Input data

CEESAR has collected 70 hours of data, using its vehicle fitted with four 128-layers rotating lidars (Ouster OS0 & OS1), six high-definition RGB cameras (Teledyne LADYBUG 6), and an IMU/GNSS device (OxTS xNAV650). All sensors are synchronized and calibrated.

Raw data from the sensors is processed to perform localization, detection, and tracking, in order to generate Omega-Prime files from the open road records. Algorithms identify interesting scenarios within these recordings. The relevant files are then used to enrich a database of driving scenarios.

3.5.1.1.1 Preprocessing

Raw data is recorded as binary files using Intempora RTMaps. Preprocessing converts this raw data into ROS2 messages. ROS2 is chosen for its convenience and the existence of many open-source projects packaged as ROS2 nodes or relying on it.

3.5.1.1.1.1 Point clouds

The first step is to preprocess point clouds from all four lidars.

Points belonging to the ego vehicle, points beyond 200m, as well as outliers are removed. A de-skewing filter is then applied to compensate for distortions caused by vehicle motion. Finally, the four corrected point clouds are concatenated into a single cloud.

3.5.1.1.1.2 Images

The lenses of the cameras introduce distortion on the images. Therefore, distortion is corrected for all images from the six cameras.

3.5.1.1.1.3 GNSS

To improve the precision of the GNSS positions, publicly available correction files (RINEX) from static GNSS stations are made available by the French National Institute of Geographic and Forest Information. These corrections are applied using NAVsolve, a software provided by OxTS.

Figure 13 Boulevard de la Vilette, Paris, Preprocessed point cloud and front image

3.5.1.1.2 Mapping

For localization, a georeferenced map of the data collection area is created. The mapping pipeline is based on the open-source project [21]. Successive lidar scans are merged using odometry and refined using the ICP algorithm.

All moving objects are then removed from the map as they may degrade localization quality.

Since most data was recorded in narrow streets, surrounded by buildings, sometimes under bridges, GNSS signals can be reflected on these obstacles, and therefore degrade GNSS precision.

In consequence, a manual rigid transformation is applied to align the point cloud with a reference map of the area. This reference map ("PCRS" map, for "Plan Corps de Rue Simplifié") is a highly accurate georeferenced map used in France to precisely locate underground and surface utility networks within public streets. It is publicly available and provided by the city of Paris.

After the rigid transformation, the map could still deviate locally from the PCRS map. To improve local alignment, we developed a tooling to distort the point cloud map.

The resulting map is then down sampled to a resolution of 1 point per m^3 to facilitate processing without degrading localization.

Figure 14 Point cloud map with PCRS map of the data collection area

An HD map (OpenDRIVE) of the area is also created. This map is not used by the processing pipeline but is required to create Omega-Prime files. It was manually drawn over PCRS maps, High Definition (5 cm) aerial imagery, and georeferenced point clouds using RoadRunner.

3.5.1.2 Processing pipeline

3.5.1.2.1 Localization

The localization pipeline relies on a factor graph [22], initialized with pose, velocity and bias constraints, to fuse and optimize trajectories from lidars, IMU and GNSS trajectories.

A scan-to-map registration algorithm, based on the normal distributions transform algorithm[23], is used to estimate the position of each scan in the map. The GNSS position provides a first estimation of the position, and the ICP algorithm refines it.

The GNSS and IMU odometry is computed by the official OxTS ROS2 Driver.

Figure 15 Result of the localization pipeline on one record

3.5.1.2.2 Detection

To detect objects surrounding the vehicle, a detection model was trained. After testing several models, a lidar and camera-based model was chosen: BEVFusion [24]. This model offers near state-of-the-art performance and provides strong classification accuracy.

The model was trained on the public nuScenes dataset and fine-tuned on approximately 1000 manually annotated frames from the collected data.

Fine-tuning the model is required because some object classes, such as stand-up scooters are not represented in public datasets.

Figure 16 Manually annotated frame

The position and state of traffic lights also need to be detected. Traffic lights are first detected in camera images using a pretrained semantic segmentation model (YOLO11). The state of each detected light is then classified using a model trained on the DriveU dataset [25] estimates the state of the detected traffic lights.

To estimate their 3D position, the resulting semantic masks are projected onto the LiDAR point clouds. Since traffic lights are represented in the OpenDRIVE map, detected lights are associated with their corresponding map entries using the Hungarian algorithm.

3.5.1.2.3 Tracking

Once objects are detected across multiple successive frames, they are tracked in order to estimate their velocity and acceleration. Since no real-time constraints are imposed, an offline tracking algorithm was implemented, based on the BiTrack tracking algorithm (Huang et al., 2025).

Detected objects are tracked using a Kalman based 3D multi object tracker, both forward and backward. These “tracklets” are then fused by aligning and reconciling their associations into a single trajectory. Conflicts are resolved using temporal overlap and detection confidence, leading to smoother and more reliable trajectories.

3.5.1.3 Results

Omega-Prime files are finally created from the OpenDRIVE map, and tracked objects, using the reference implementation from RHTW Aachen.

This file format was chosen because it is independent of the data source and relies on existing standards (see part 3.3.2).

These files are then used to detect driving scenarios based on conditions such as relative positions, position in a lane, or speed.

CEESAR has collected more than 70 hours of data in urban environment. A complete processing pipeline was developed to precisely locate the collection vehicle, detect surrounding objects, classify traffic lights, and track detected objects. The outputs of the pipeline are Omega-Prime

files, containing detected moving objects, traffic lights information, and an OpenDRIVE semantic map. Driving scenarios are then extracted from these files to enrich scenario databases.

3.5.2 Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH

3.5.2.1 Objective

Validation and testing of automated driving functions require access to realistic multi-actor traffic scenarios. One common source of such scenarios is recordings from instrumented test vehicles equipped with on-board sensors and perception systems. However, such measurements are rarely suitable for direct use in simulation environments. Three classes of data quality issues routinely arise:

- **Measurement noise:** Object state estimates are inherently noisy. For the sensors used in the current project, the position noise standard deviation is approximately 0.5 m (front radar) and 1 m (rear radar). Over a multi-second recording this noise is clearly visible as jitter in the reported trajectory and, if left uncorrected, produces unnatural vehicle motion in the simulation.
- **Measurement gaps:** Sensor/Perception system detections are not guaranteed at every sampling instant. Temporary occlusions, low radar cross-section, or sensor self-interference can produce stretches of missing data ranging from a single sample to several seconds of missing samples.
- **Outliers:** Multi-path reflections or false detections occasionally produce single-sample position shifts that are physically implausible given the dynamics of road vehicles.

These issues motivate the use of a dedicated reconstruction step that maps the noisy, and possibly incomplete measurement sequence onto a smooth, gap-free, physically consistent trajectory at a uniform sampling rate. The reconstructed trajectory can then be reliably used by downstream modules that generate OpenSCENARIO event descriptions, speed profiles, and actor definitions for simulation.

3.5.2.2 Input data

The format of the input data is determined by the requirements of the Scenario Generation and Reconstruction Tool. Since trajectory reconstruction is one of the functionalities provided by the tool, the input must conform to the same structure expected across all tool operations. Concretely, the user is expected to provide object-level data: state information of tracked objects (position, orientation, and optionally velocity) together with corresponding timestamps for each sample.

The tool accepts two input file formats: `.json` and `.mcap`. In both cases, the data must follow a hierarchical structure that reflects the tool's internal data class. At the top level, the structure distinguishes between vehicles acting as ego platforms, each of which may carry one or more on-board sensors. For each sensor, the structure holds an array of trajectory samples for each tracked object. Each sample must contain at minimum the fields `x`, `y`, and `time_s` (position in a local Cartesian coordinate frame in metres, and timestamp in seconds). The fields `z`, `heading`, `pitch`, and `roll` are also expected; if unavailable they may be set to zero and will be carried through unchanged. Note that the heading field will be overwritten by the value reconstructed by the algorithm. The expected structure is illustrated below:

```
"data_type": "trajectory_data",
```

```

"data": {
  "<ego_vehicle_id>": {
    "<sensor_id>": {
      "trajectories": [
        {"x": <num>, "y": <num>, "z": <num>,
        "heading": <num>, "pitch": <num>, "roll": <num>,
        "time_s": <num>},
        ...
      ]
    },
    ...
  },
  ...
}

```

The tool does not require the input sequence to be gap-free or sampled at a uniform rate. Missing detections are handled natively by the reconstruction algorithm, which simply omits missing timesteps from the measurement terms of the optimisation problem. Pre-interpolation of the trajectory is therefore not necessary.

The tool supports multi-vehicle recordings in which several vehicles simultaneously act as ego platforms, each tracking objects within their own field of view. This is particularly relevant for vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) use cases, where multiple vehicles with overlapping fields of view observe the same objects. For each ego vehicle, measurements from multiple sensors can be provided and used jointly during reconstruction. When multiple sensors observe the same object, the reconstruction algorithm combines their measurements automatically, and the quality of the result generally improves with the number of available measurement sources. Users are therefore encouraged to enable all available sensors for reconstruction rather than selecting a single source.

The current version of the reconstruction functionality assumes that object matching has already been performed prior to import, meaning each tracked object carries a unique identifier that is consistent across sensors and time. Cross-sensor association and ego-to-object matching are outside the scope of the tool and must be handled in a pre-processing step.

Finally, prior knowledge about the sensor noise characteristics (e.g. position standard deviation) and the expected operational design domain (ODD) of the scenario is beneficial for configuring the algorithm's hyperparameters. Guidance on how this information can be used for hyperparameter selection is provided in the subsequent subsections.

3.5.2.3 Processing pipeline

3.5.2.3.1 Motion models

The reconstruction is based on motion models with kinematic (propagated) process noise formulation. Currently, algorithm supports constant velocity (CV) and constant velocity and turn

rate (CTRV) models with extensions of the model catalogue planned as new measurement recordings become available. The general discrete-time state equation can be defined as:

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = g(\mathbf{x}_k) + \mathbf{L}\mathbf{v}_k,$$

where g represents the state \mathbf{x}_k evolution function, which for the linear case (e.g. CV model) can be reduced to a matrix form $g(\mathbf{x}_k) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_k$. The process noise \mathbf{v}_k represents the unmodelled state variables that are seen as the source of deviation from the assumptions made by the motion model choice. In the simple case of a CV model, the process noise would represent acceleration along the x- and y-axis, which would result in the change of the corresponding velocity states.

In addition to the motion models, the user can choose different measurement models that can be generally described with the equation:

$$\mathbf{z}_k = h(\mathbf{x}_k) + \mathbf{w}_k,$$

where h represents the sensor function, while \mathbf{w}_k represents the additive sensor noise. The current version of the algorithm was tested assuming measurements are recorded at the object-level, containing information about the states of the tracked objects. This resulted in rewriting of the function h as a matrix C with non-zero elements corresponding to the recorded state variables. Depending on the availability of the measurements' sources, the proposed reconstruction algorithm can consider multiple sensors at the same time with varying sensor functions and noise profiles.

It should be noted that the process and sensor noise are assumed to be i.i.d. and reflect how much does the user trust the sensors and adopted motion model. The algorithm tests conducted so far have assumed that the process and sensor noise profiles follow zero-mean normal distribution with fixed standard deviations. These standard deviations are used to populate the process \mathbf{Q} and sensor \mathbf{R} matrices.

3.5.2.3.2 Moving Horizon Estimation (MHE)

The reconstruction algorithm relies on Moving Horizon Estimation (MHE), a state estimation method capturing the motion of objects within windows of constant width. At each step i , a window of N consecutive timesteps is considered and the following constrained optimisation problem is solved:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{x}_i, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{i+N}, \mathbf{v}_i, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{i+N-1}} & \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=i}^{k=i+N-1} \rho_{st}(\mathbf{M}\mathbf{v}_k) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{k=i}^{k=i+N} \rho_m(\mathbf{N}\mathbf{w}_k^j) \\ \text{s. t. } & \mathbf{x}_{i+1} = g(\mathbf{x}_i) + \mathbf{L}\mathbf{v}_i, \\ & \mathbf{z}_i = h(\mathbf{x}_i) + \mathbf{w}_i^j, \\ & j = 1, \dots, m. \end{aligned}$$

The ρ_{st} and ρ_m represent robust loss functions applied element-wise to the noise residuals scaled by the matrices \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{N} , which are derived from covariance matrices \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} respectively. The first term penalises large process-noise realisations and controls trajectory smoothness. The second term penalises deviations from the available measurements for all m available sensors, where missing measurements are simply omitted from the sum.

The optimality conditions of this constrained problem form a linear Karush–Kuhn–Tucker (KKT) system that is assembled from fixed sparse blocks (built once per actor) and solved using a sparse direct solver. The window then slides by one timestep and the procedure repeats until the full trajectory is covered. The output is a dense state sequence at the sensor's nominal sampling rate, with the estimated positions and velocities at every timestep regardless of whether a measurement was available there.

3.5.2.3.3 Robust Loss Functions and IRLS

A key feature of the implementation is support for robust loss functions that reduce the influence of different noise profiles and outliers. Currently, the algorithm provides support for five options:

- L2: Standard least squares norm - assumed for Gaussian noise distribution without outliers anticipated.
- L1: Absolute norm – Robust, but not smooth at zero.
- Huber: Quadratic near zero, linear in the tails. Requires definition of threshold parameter M .
- Geman-McClure: Saturates for large residuals and strongly outlier-robust.
- Barron: Generalised loss parameterised by shape α and scale c . Can be reduced to L2 ($\alpha = 2$), Cauchy ($\alpha = 0$), or Welsch variants at other values. While most flexible, it requires two hyperparameter definitions.

For non-quadratic losses, the optimisation is solved by Iteratively Reweighted Least Squares (IRLS). At each iteration the loss is linearised by assigning a scalar weight calculated as $\frac{\rho(\mathbf{r}_k)}{\mathbf{r}_k}$ to each residual \mathbf{r}_k , and the resulting KKT system is solved. The solution from iteration t provides updated residuals r_{t+1} for the next iteration. Note that the number of IRLS iterations is a hyperparameter that should be set in accordance with the chosen loss function.

3.5.2.4 Integration in the Scenario Reconstruction and Generation Tool

3.5.2.4.1 Processing pipeline

The tool processes scenario recordings through a configurable pipeline of four stages:

1. Import JSON/MCAP files – load scenario data including actors, corresponding trajectories and map reference.
2. Data Modification (applied in user-defined order) – Beside described Trajectory Reconstruction, user can perform some additional modifications such as shifting the position of the reference point, changing the start and stop time, etc.
3. Data Filtering – User can choose which actors and their corresponding trajectories should be modified and stored in the final output file.
4. Output Generation – The filtered and modified trajectories will be used to generate an OpenSCENARIO (.xosc) file with additional option to visualize and save the resulting trajectories as a figure.

In step 2, the TrajectoryReconstruction modifier is applied per actor and each actor in the loaded scenario may carry measurements from multiple sensor types (e.g., front radar, rear radar). Generally, the quality of the reconstruction would improve with the use of multiple measurement sources, but the user is provided with an option to exclude a certain sensor from the reconstruction process.

3.5.2.4.2 GUI controls

The Trajectory Reconstruction modifier is accessible from the “Data Modify” tab of the tool. Figure 17 shows the current layout of the tab with an example scenario loaded.

Figure 17 Data Modify tap with Trajectory Reconstruction section enclosed within the red rectangle. Upon selection of the hyperparameter values, the reconstruction is initiated clicking on Start button (bottom right).

The Trajectory Reconstruction section presents the following controls:

- Horizon width: — integer input field for the window size N .
- IRLS iterations — integer input field for the number of reweighting iterations.
- Process noise Q (diagonal) — float input field for the scalar sq .
- Loss function — dropdown menu; selecting Huber or Barron reveals the
 - corresponding parameter fields dynamically.
 - Huber M (visible when Huber selected) — float input for the Huber threshold.
 - Barron alpha/ Barron c (visible when Barron selected) — float inputs for the Barron shape and scale parameters.

All settings are persisted automatically to the tool's settings file and restored on the next launch.

3.5.2.5 Results

The output of the reconstruction step is a dense, uniformly sampled state sequence that replaces the original trajectory data within the tool's internal data class. Compared to the raw input, the reconstructed trajectories are smoother and represent physically feasible object motion continuously defined over the full recording timebase, including intervals where measurements were absent. When only position measurements are available, the algorithm additionally estimates the heading angle at each timestep from the reconstructed velocity states. This estimated heading overwrites the heading field of the original data. It should be noted that the reconstruction output is stored in place — the original noisy measurements are not retained separately — and the resulting trajectories are directly passed to the downstream export step to generate the OpenSCENARIO file.

To illustrate the reconstruction capability under different data quality conditions, four representative cases were constructed using recordings from the measurement campaign conducted as part of WP3. Each case was designed to highlight a specific challenge commonly encountered in measurement processing:

Case 1 — High measurement noise. Figure 2 shows the reconstruction result for the test vehicle trajectory corrupted with zero-mean Gaussian noise of $\sigma = 1.5$ m applied independently to both

position axes. The L2 loss function was used with the default hyperparameter values ($N = 100$, $Q = 100$), which assumed that the available horizon width includes 2 s of the measurements. The reconstructed trajectory achieves a mean distance of 0.23 m and RMSE of 0.35 m from the ground truth — a noise reduction by a factor of approximately six relative to the injected standard deviation. The error-over-time panel reveals a slightly elevated deviation in the first two seconds of the recording, which is attributable to the initial velocity estimate: with noisy measurements at a 0.02 s sampling interval, even a regression over the first horizon window introduces a small transient before the estimator converges to the correct state. Beyond this initial interval, the error remains consistently below 0.5 m and well within the injected noise band.

Figure 18 Demonstration of the results for the measurements corrupted with noise of Gaussian profile

Case 2 — Outliers. Figure 3 presents the result for the trajectory with a small percentage of large-displacement outlier samples injected, representing multi-path reflections or false detections. The Huber loss function was selected with its default threshold parameter ($M = 1.345$), and the reconstruction achieves a mean distance of 0.15 m to the ground truth. As visible from the x-y path and time panels, the reconstructed trajectory is largely indistinguishable from the ground truth despite the presence of outliers, confirming that the Huber loss successfully downweights the outlier residuals without requiring manual threshold tuning. Notably, the default value of M is already effective for the noise level present in this recording, consistent with the guideline that $M \approx 1.345 \cdot \sigma$ provides near-optimal robustness under near-Gaussian conditions.

Figure 19 Demonstration of the results for the measurements corrupted with outliers

Case 3 — Measurement gaps. Figure 4 illustrates the algorithm's gap-filling capability. Three gaps of approximately 0.52 s duration each were introduced at $t \approx [0.9, 8.1, 12.0]$ s by removing all measurements within those intervals (no additional noise was injected). The reconstruction achieves a mean distance of 0.02 m and maximum distance of 0.06 m, effectively recovering the ground truth trajectory through all three gaps. This near-perfect result reflects the key property of the MHE formulation: missing measurements are simply absent from the measurement cost term, and the motion model propagates the state estimate continuously through the gap, producing a physically consistent interpolation without any special gap-handling logic.

Figure 20 Demonstration of the results for the measurements containing time gaps

Case 4 — Combined noise, outliers, and gaps. Figure 5 presents the most challenging case, in which all three degradations were applied simultaneously to represent a realistic worst-case measurement scenario. Using the Huber loss function, the reconstruction achieves a mean distance of 0.27 m and RMSE of 0.36 m, which is only marginally worse than Case 1 alone — indicating that the addition of outliers and gaps does not significantly degrade performance when an appropriate loss function is selected. The error profile is broadly similar to Case 1, with a small initial transient and stable tracking thereafter. The maximum distance of 1.63 m occurs at an isolated timestep and is consistent with a horizon boundary effect at the location of one of the injected gaps.

Figure 21 Demonstration of results for measurements containing all three expected challenges (noise, outliers, and time gaps)

As additional measurement data becomes available from the ongoing WP3 measurement campaign, further reconstruction results will be reported in future tool-related deliverables.

These four cases demonstrate the reconstruction functionality against typical challenges encountered in measurement processing. A key factor contributing to the quality of each result is the appropriate tuning of the algorithm's hyperparameters. Therefore, some practical tuning guidelines compiled from testing on the internally available recordings are provided below.

3.5.2.5.1 Hyperparameter Description and Tuning

Horizon Width N

The MHE window covers $N\Delta t$ seconds of data at a time. A wider window gives the estimator more context when filling gaps and smoothing noise, at the cost of proportionally higher computation per step.

Tuning guidance:

- For highway and motorway scenarios (relatively smooth trajectories), 2-5 seconds provides a good starting point.

- Reduce N if the scenario contains sharp manoeuvres (aggressive lane changes, emergency braking) where the constant-velocity assumption breaks down over long windows.
- N must be smaller than the total number of timesteps; the modifier will skip actors that do not satisfy this condition and print a warning.

IRLS iterations

The number of times the per-residual weights are recomputed and the KKT system re-solved within each horizon.

Tuning guidance:

- For the L2 loss, one iteration is exact (no reweighting needed); additional iterations have no effect and only add computational cost.
- For L1, Huber, Geman–McClure, and Barron, convergence in practice requires 5–10 iterations. The gain diminishes quickly after 10 iterations in typical road scenarios.

Process noise Q (diagonal)

The covariance $Q = q \cdot I$ governs the trade-off between trajectory smoothness and fidelity to the measurements:

- High q : large process-noise budget, allowing the estimated velocity to change rapidly. The reconstruction tracks the measurements more closely and exhibits less smoothing but may retain more noise.
- Low q : tight process-noise constraint, enforcing near-constant velocity. The result is very smooth but may not capture genuine acceleration events.

Tuning guidance: Start with the default value of 100. If the reconstructed trajectory visibly lags behind measurements during turning or braking, increase the value of the hyperparameter. Otherwise, if the reconstruction appears noisy despite a robust loss function, decrease q .

Loss functions and their parameters.

The following table provides suggestions when to use currently supported loss functions.

Table 9 Loss function parameters

Scenario	Recommended loss function
Clean measurements, Gaussian noise profile	L2
Occasional outliers (e.g. 5-10% of samples)	Huber
Frequent or large outliers	Geman-McClure
Unknown noise distribution, experimental phase	Barron
Very sparse measurements with many gaps	L1 or Huber

Huber parameter M

The threshold M separates the quadratic region from the linear tail of the distribution. A value of $M = 1.345 \cdot \hat{\sigma}$, where $\hat{\sigma}$ is an estimate of the measurement noise standard deviation, gives 95 % efficiency relative to L2 under Gaussian noise while providing robustness to outliers.

Barron parameters α and c

The shape parameter α controls the tail behaviour. For moderate outlier robustness, α can be set in range (0,1). The scale parameter c plays a role analogous to the Huber M : residuals larger than c are downweighed. Set c to be on the order of the expected measurement noise standard deviation.

3.5.2.6 Conclusion

The trajectory reconstruction functionality presented in this document addresses a critical pre-processing step in the pipeline from raw sensor recordings to simulation-ready scenario descriptions. By mapping noisy, incomplete measurement sequences onto smooth, gap-free, and physically consistent trajectories, the algorithm ensures that the output OpenSCENARIO files represent object motion that is both numerically stable and dynamically plausible — a prerequisite for their reliable use in simulation and testing of automated driving and ADAS functions.

From the perspective of semantic relevance, the reconstruction step plays a central role in preserving and restoring the semantic content of the original recording. The tool retains the semantic context of the scenario throughout the pipeline — actor identities, road network reference, and scenario structure are carried from the raw input through to the OpenSCENARIO output unchanged. Furthermore, semantic knowledge about the scenario itself — such as the road type, speed regime, and expected manoeuvre class — directly informs both the choice of motion model and the tuning of the reconstruction hyperparameters. For example, a highway convoy scenario with smooth, near-constant-velocity motion calls for different window widths and process noise settings than an urban intersection scenario with sharp turning manoeuvres. In this sense, the semantic characterisation of a scenario is not only relevant to its downstream use in simulation, but also serves as a practical input to the reconstruction process itself.

With respect to interoperability, the reconstruction algorithm has been integrated into the Scenario Generation and Reconstruction Tool, which is being developed as part of WP5 and relies on measurement data generated through the WP3 measurement campaign. On the input side, the tool supports both JSON and MCAP/ROS2 file formats, ensuring compatibility with the diverse measurement setups used across project partners. On the output side, the use of the OpenSCENARIO standard as the export format provides a direct interoperability pathway to a wide range of simulation platforms. As scenario recordings from both VIF's dataset and those made available by project partners are processed, the reconstruction pipeline will contribute to building a comprehensive dataset of OpenSCENARIO files that can serve as a shared resource for the simulation and testing of future AD and ADAS functions across the consortium.

Looking ahead, the core reconstruction functionality has been developed and demonstrated against representative data quality challenges. As further measurement data from the WP3 campaign becomes available, the set of tested and reported scenarios will expand, and new reconstruction challenges may emerge that motivate targeted extensions to the algorithm — in particular the addition of nonlinear motion models such as CTRV and CTRA, which are better suited to scenarios involving sustained turning manoeuvres. Multi-sensor fusion, combining

measurements from sensors with overlapping fields of view, is a further planned extension that will require input from the measurement campaign on sensor characterisation and reference-point offsets. In parallel, development efforts will increasingly focus on improving the user experience: this includes guided hyperparameter selection based on automated data quality indicators, and enhanced in-tool visualisation of reconstruction results to support iterative tuning.

3.5.3 Vicomtech

3.5.3.1 Objective

Object detectors measure positions in a timely manner with a frequency determined by construction. Detectors do not provide any consistent identification of objects. To extend the applicability of automatic systems in the self-driving context, we employ tracking. Tracking enhances detections in two aspects: 1) by providing an object identification, 2) it allows to compute the time derivatives of the object positions.

In the Task 4.2, we implemented an algorithm of tracking-by-detection. The implementation is available through the main Python registry under the name `kinematic-tracker`. The documentation of the library can be found on Github [26].

The tracking-by-detection can create, keep and eliminate *identified* targets when given a list of detections regularly. In the self-driving context, the number of tracked targets varies, so the technique is commonly referred as multiple-object-tracking (MOT) or multiple-target-tracking (MTT).

The implemented algorithm is based on Kalman filters. It is sufficiently general to cover any number of dimensions, including 2D and 3D cases relevant for self-driving. Kalman filtering is a well-known technique developed by Rudolf Kalman around 1960. Modern presentation of the technique is covered in numerous textbooks and practical guides. Here, we will briefly remind the theory behind the Kalman filtering as much as it is relevant for discussing our contributions.

Kalman filter allows to mitigate the detector noise and calculate the time derivatives. It is a foundation of the tracking algorithm we implemented. However, the identification part of the burden is solved by *association algorithms*. In this project, we developed an original association metric superior to the popular intersection-over-union (IoU) association metric in terms of the accuracy and computation performance.

3.5.3.2 Processing pipeline

3.5.3.2.1 Multiple-object tracking: birds-eye view

Trackers provide identification to the input detections by maintaining a history of detections. In the simplest case, the history consists of a single (latest) time instance. Given the time to the latest detection, it is possible to derive kinematic characteristics of the targets as well as estimate the next measurement with some degree of confidence. The predictions of the next measurement and estimation of their expected deviations are at the core of the Kalman filtering approach. In the Kalman filter approach, an object measurement is represented as a vector \mathbf{z} . To have an example for the measurement vector, let's consider 2D detections of cars in a video stream. Such detections are typically given by bounding boxes aligned with image axes. For the sake of tracking, such bounding boxes are encoded by the *position* of their centres and their *sizes*: $\mathbf{z} = (p_x, p_y, s_x, s_y)$ i.e. four variables per bounding box. To represent the confidence of the

measurement, a covariance matrix is used. The covariance matrix is principally an expectation value of the products of differences for all variable-pairs $R_{ij} = E((z_i - E(z_i))(z_j - E(z_j)))$. The expectation value $E(x)$ is statistical ensemble average. The covariance matrix in practice is often estimated ad-hoc, subject for a posterior justification. Given the time sampling, it is straightforward to estimate the velocities and accelerations of the targets. Typically, the targets are described by their *state* vectors which include positions, sizes and possibly their time derivatives (velocities and accelerations). In our example of 2D tracking, the state vector could be $\mathbf{x} = (p_x, v_x, p_y, v_y, s_x, s_y)$, where apart from the measurement variables, we included velocities of the bounding-box positions to the state vector. Conversely, the estimation of the state covariance will be given by a 6 by 6 matrix P_{ij} . The task of a Kalman filter is to provide an estimation of the target state and its covariance given the measurement vector and covariance

$$\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{P} = \text{KF}(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{R})$$

In this project, we use so-called linear Kalman filters. For linear Kalman filters, the estimation of the state evolution is linear as well as the relation between measurement vectors and target states is linear: $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}(t + dt) = \mathbf{F}(dt)\mathbf{x}(t)$ and $\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x}$. Here the fundamental \mathbf{F} and measurement \mathbf{H} matrices are introduced. For the fundamental matrices we use *kinematic* models: *constant position* (CP), *constant velocity* (CV) and *constant acceleration* (CA) models applied independently for each of the Cartesian dimensions are the most popular. The form of the measurement matrix follows from the choice of the fundamental matrix.

The estimation of the state covariance is a two-stage calculation. Firstly, the current state is propagated by the time step dt to give a predicted estimation of the state $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}(t + dt)$ and its covariance $\tilde{\mathbf{P}} = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{P}\mathbf{F}^T + \mathbf{Q}$. Secondly, the estimated state and covariance are corrected by considering the measurement vector \mathbf{z} and its covariance \mathbf{R} :

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{U}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}, \tilde{\mathbf{P}}, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{R}) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{P} = \mathbf{C}(\tilde{\mathbf{P}}, \mathbf{R})$$

The matrix functions \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{C} are elementary albeit too voluminous to spell out here. Our main concern, however, is the process-noise covariance \mathbf{Q} appearing in the first stage.

Process-noise is an additive modification of the predicted uncertainties to consider external perturbances accumulated between measurements. The process-noise covariance \mathbf{Q} is often chosen ad-hoc and tuned based on the responsiveness of the updates and apparent noise reduction in the derivatives. In this project, we developed an original adaptive process-noise model which eliminates the need for the tuning. Please, find the details of developed process-noise model below in this report.

We briefly described the linear Kalman filters above. Kalman filters are an important building block to formulate MOT. A second build block indispensable in formulation of the MOT is the procedure of *association*. Indeed, because the detections arrive unidentified, we need to establish some correspondence between the predictions $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}(t + dt)$ and detections \mathbf{z} before we commence the second (update) stage of the filtering.

The association procedure starts with computation of all likelihoods between sets of predictions and detections. Since the number of detections and targets vary independently to a certain extent, the matrix of likelihoods is generally rectangular. Having the matrix of likelihoods, we run into a problem of computing a bipartite matching. The bipartite matching is solved in the discrete mathematics with several algorithms. In the kinematic tracker we describe, the bipartite matching can be established with the straightforward Greedy algorithm or with the non-local linear-sum assignment approach. The last approach is commonly referred as Hungarian algorithm. Both matching algorithms are easy to implement if using the modern SciPy library.

The computation of the matrices of likelihoods is less standard. We implemented several popular likelihood models, described below in this report.

3.5.3.2 Adaptive process-noise covariance

The process-noise covariance is an additive correction of the noise covariance of the state prediction at the first stage of Kalman filtering. The process-noise models are notoriously difficult to construct and tune. In this project, we base our development on the so-called white-noise models. The covariance matrices of the white-noise models are derived assuming the process-noise covariance zero everywhere except the highest-derivatives matrix element. The non-zero covariance in the highest-derivatives matrix element leads to the appearance of the covariance in the rest of the matrix elements at later times. Conversely, the final white-noise covariance could be calculated by integrating of the predicted covariance to the time step:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}(dt) = \int_0^{dt} \mathbf{F}(\tau) \mathbf{Q}_0 \mathbf{F}^T(\tau) d\tau$$

The matrices $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}(dt)$ are easy to compute for all relevant point-motion models. The final process-noise model contains just one tuneable parameter: the seed covariance in the highest-derivatives matrix element. To have a formula in front of our eyes, we spell out the white-noise model explicitly, for the constant-velocity point-motion model. The fundamental matrix for the

constant-velocity point-motion model is $\mathbf{F} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \Delta t \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$. Conversely, the white-noise covariance is $\mathbf{Q} = \Phi \begin{pmatrix} \Delta t^3/3 & \Delta t^2/2 \\ \Delta t^2/2 & \Delta t \end{pmatrix}$, where the Φ is the seed covariance (square of standard velocity deviation).

Despite the appearance of different powers of time step, the white-noise covariance model possesses natural addition property

$$\mathbf{F}(t_2) \mathbf{Q}(t_1) \mathbf{F}^T(t_2) + \mathbf{Q}(t_2) = \mathbf{Q}(t_1 + t_2).$$

Apart from its plausibility, the addition property makes it possible to establish the form of the white-noise covariance model for multi-dimensional case. Namely, the property could be preserved only when any cross-dimension matrix elements are zero.

Despite having just one free parameter, the white-noise model is still difficult to choose. The quality of the predictions is highly sensitive to the choice of the constant.

Our solution to the problem starts by doing optimization of the factor Φ for one-dimensional harmonic motion with added pseudo-normal measurement noise. Several tracking examples were averaged before solving the optimization problem. Effectively, the optimal factors were determined for the whole tracking, without any attempt to tune the factor Φ in each of the steps. Effectively, this approach is a Monte-Carlo simulation of the statistical ensemble produced by the kinematic Kalman filters. The result shows that the only possibility for the optimal choice in the static problem is proportional to the derivative of the order one higher than available in the state vector. Apart from the higher derivative, the factor Φ is proportional to the highest derivative present in the state vector. For example, in the CV model, the optimal static factor is $\Phi = c|av|$, where the pre-factor c is constant across all the harmonic-motion albeit is not unity. The terms in the absolute value are maximal values of acceleration and velocity dictated by the harmonic motion. The pre-factor for the optimal static tracking is $c \sim 0.12$. For the CV model, the highest derivative present in the state vector is velocity v and the next-order higher derivative is acceleration a . Similar choice proves to be working for all motion models. For CP model, the

optimal static factor is $\Phi = c|v|$, for the CV model $\Phi = c|av|$, for the CA model $\Phi = c|aj|$, where j is the maximal value of the fourth derivative of the position (jerk).

To finalize the adaptive model, we use the instant values of derivatives instead of their maximal values available only in the harmonic motion models. Using the instant values, we found that the optimal value of the pre-factor c becomes unity. The instant derivatives of higher order missing in the Kalman states we estimate by employing finite differences and running averages applied to the last available derivatives.

The approach described above is not published in any peer-review journal albeit it has been tested in many applications and open-sourced in the kinematic tracker.

3.5.3.2.3 Association metrics

The association metrics might be split into two types: Mahalanobis-distance based and intersection-over-union (IoU) based. The association likelihoods based on Mahalanobis distance are perhaps the most natural in Kalman-filter tracking. Indeed, the Mahalanobis distance directly relates to Gaussian probability distribution which are at the core of the Kalman filtering.

Having two estimations of the same measurement vector z_1, R_1 and z_2, R_2 we can define a statistically significant distance between them $D_{21} = \sqrt{(z_2 - z_1)(R_1 + R_2)^{-1}(z_2 - z_1)^T}$.

After running the first stage of the Kalman filter, we have predictions of the states \tilde{x}_i, \tilde{P}_i and measurements z_j, R_j . Using the definition of the measurement matrix H we can arrive at working definition for the association Mahalanobis distance $D_{ij} = \sqrt{(H\tilde{x}_i - z_j)C_{ij}^{-1}(H\tilde{x}_i - z_j)^T}$, where the *Kalman-filter covariance* reads

$$C_{ij} = H\tilde{P}_iH^T + R_j.$$

Finally, the likelihood will be $L_{ij} = \exp^{-D_{ij}^2/(2N)}$, where N is the number of degrees of freedom in the measurement vector. The number of degrees of freedom N ensures the well-behaving values of the likelihoods because the ensemble averages of the square Mahalanobis distances are equal to number of variables.

Unfortunately, the Mahalanobis distances prove to be less reliable comparing to the pure-geometric, IoU-based metrics. The IoU-based metrics are defined via ratios of intersection areas or volumes to the union areas or volumes for 2D or 3D cases correspondingly. Moreover, the concept is generalized (GloU) to the case when there is no intersection by constructing a ratio with convex-hull areas or volumes. The IoU-based metrics disregard the noise covariance available in the Kalman filtering approach effectively using sizes of the bounding boxes or cuboids as unit of measure. A downside of the IoU-based metrics is their complexity for implementation if comparing to the arithmetically homogeneous Mahalanobis distances.

Motivated by the success of the IoU-based metrics and striving to maintain the simplicity of the Mahalanobis-distance metrics, we suggest two variants of Mahalanobis-based metrics. First variant is using square Mahalanobis distance and a size-modulated diagonal covariance. Second variant uses the Mahalanobis distance directly and GloU as calibration reference.

Indeed, it is easy to come up with covariance that would scale with size of the objects, rather than using the Kalman-filter covariance C_{ij} . The first variant relies on a diagonal covariance addition constructed from average square sizes. In other words, we add a size-modulated covariance matrix to the regular Kalman-filter covariance matrix $\tilde{C}_{ij} = C_{ij} + M_{ij}$. The *size-modulated* covariance M_{ij} is the diagonal matrix featuring average of square sizes in both

locations: positions and sizes. For instance, in the example of 2D tracking defined by the measurement vector $\mathbf{z} = (p_x, p_y, s_x, s_y)$, the size-modulated covariance reads

$$M_{ij} = \frac{1}{4} \begin{pmatrix} s_{xi}^2 + s_{xj}^2 & & & \\ & s_{yi}^2 + s_{yj}^2 & & \\ & & s_{xi}^2 + s_{xj}^2 & \\ & & & s_{yi}^2 + s_{yj}^2 \end{pmatrix}.$$

This size-modulated Mahalanobis metric is implemented in the kinematic tracker. It has shown excellent results in many applications. It is worth nothing that the size-modulated Mahalanobis metric is more cumbersome to define than the original Kalman-filter metric. The complication comes from the fact that one must be aware of the meaning of the variables in the measurement vectors to define the size-modulated covariance. On the bright side, the size-modulated Mahalanobis metric remains to be much less complicated than the IoU-based association metrics.

The size-modulated Mahalanobis association metric ignores the rotation degrees of freedom common in the 3D tracking. To fill the gap, we suggest another variant of the size-modulated metric. To define this variant, we largely abandon the usual definition of the association covariance. Instead, we use the GloU as a calibration reference and define the inversion of the covariance matrix (precision matrix) for calculation of the Mahalanobis distance. Additionally, we chose to maintain the IoU-based metrics' insensitivity to 180° rotations. Although technically a defect, it serves as a practical advantage because *current* detectors often predict flipped orientations. However, this designed rotational ambiguity can be easily removed if required.

Let's define the association metric for the nuScenes measurement vectors. The nuScenes measurement vectors feature positions, rotations and sizes in this order, while rotations are represented with quaternions

$$\mathbf{z} = (p_x, p_y, p_z, w, r_x, r_y, r_z, s_x, s_y, s_z) \text{ or, for a shorter notation, } \mathbf{z} = (\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{s}).$$

To define the variable differences, we use algebraic differences for all Cartesian components and a geodesic difference for rotations

$$\mathbf{z}_i - \mathbf{z}_j = (\mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{p}_j, \omega_{ij}, \mathbf{s}_i - \mathbf{s}_j),$$

where a doubled and wrapped geodesic distance between two quaternions is used ω_{ij}

$$\omega_{ij} = \begin{cases} \theta_{ij} & \text{if } \theta_{ij} < \pi \\ 2\pi - \theta_{ij} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \text{ where } \theta_{ij} = 4 \arccos(\mathbf{q}_i \mathbf{q}_j)$$

The difference vectors $\mathbf{z}_i - \mathbf{z}_j = (\mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{p}_j, \omega_{ij}, \mathbf{s}_i - \mathbf{s}_j)$ have 7 variables. Conversely, we define a size-modulated, diagonal precision matrix \mathbf{P}^{ij} of shape 7 by 7

$$\mathbf{P}^{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} a\mathbf{S}_{ij} & & \\ & b & \\ & & c\mathbf{S}_{ij} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Here, we ensure size modulation by the inverse squares of cuboid sizes $\mathbf{S}_{ij} = (\mathbf{s}_i + \mathbf{s}_j)^{-2}$. The matrices \mathbf{S}_{ij} are diagonal of shapes 3 by 3. The calibration coefficients a , b and c remain in the precision matrix \mathbf{P}^{ij} . These calibration coefficients will be determined at the end of the definition.

Having the difference vectors $\mathbf{z}_i - \mathbf{z}_j$ and the size-modulated precision matrices \mathbf{P}^{ij} defined, we proceed further and compute the Mahalanobis distance $D_{ij} = \sqrt{(\mathbf{z}_i - \mathbf{z}_j)^2 \mathbf{P}^{ij}}$. It is worth nothing that the product under the square root is essentially a scalar vector product and we avoided matrix inversion normally present in the Mahalanobis distance.

Now, we must decide on the definition of the likelihood L_{ij} . The regular likelihood $L_{ij} = \exp^{-D_{ij}^2/(2N)}$ uses the square Mahalanobis distance D_{ij}^2 . Although this definition directly follows from the Gaussian probability density, we will have a better comparison with GloU metrics when using the first power of the Mahalanobis distance $L_{ij} = \exp^{-D_{ij}}$. The normalization pre-factors ($2N$) will be absorbed to the calibration constants a , b and c .

It remains to define the calibration constants. We accomplish this by equating out likelihood L_{ij} to the GloU metric at three (reference) cuboid configurations. We have chosen these cuboid configurations *orthogonal* to each other. To calibrate the *translation* coefficient a , we choose a configuration when the two unit-size boxes differ by a 3-unit translation along one of the Cartesian axes. This configuration is at the $\frac{1}{4}$ cutoff normally implied in the association procedure. To calibrate the rotation coefficient b , we choose a configuration when two cuboids of the same size $3 \times 1 \times 1$ are positioned at the origin and rotated relative to each other by 45° . To calibrate the scaling coefficient c , we choose a configuration when both cuboids are at the origin and not rotated, while one of the cuboids is unit-sized and the other is twice larger along two of the Cartesian axes.

We conducted comparisons between different association metrics in two ways: a visual and interactive comparison and a quantitative assessment in the tracking. The interactive comparison is implemented in a little GUI application **association-studio** available from the main Python package registry PyPI. The **association-studio** allows to move and rotate two rectangles while computing and bar-plotting the association metrics provided by the **kinematic-tracker**. A screenshot of the application is given below.

Figure 22 Kinematic tracker

The quantitative comparison, the is done by tracking of the annotations from the nuScenes dataset using the kinematic tracker. The evaluation of the association quality has been done with an original binary classification approach via instrumented association. The classification approach acronymic is ClavIA alluding to *Classification Via Instrumented Association*. The classification approach is open-sourced and currently under review with a preprint available **iError! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..**

3.5.3.3 Input data

To perform multiple-object tracking, the kinematic-tracker library requires two primary sets of inputs: dynamic frame data and algorithmic configuration parameters.

3.5.3.3.1 Dynamic Frame Data

This consists of a regular, time-stamped sequence of unidentified object detections. For each new frame, the tracker requires:

- **Time step:** The elapsed time since the previous frame, used to propagate the kinematic state.
- **Measurement vectors:** The spatial dimensions of the detected objects. This can be a 4-variable 2D bounding box or a 7-variable 3D nuScenes cuboid where positions, sizes, and rotation quaternions are specified.
- **Measurement covariance matrix:** An ad-hoc or sensor-derived matrix representing the expected noise and tracking deviations for each variable in the measurement vector.

3.5.3.3.2 Algorithmic Configuration

Before running the pipeline, the user must initialize the tracker with specific behavioral rules:

- **Motion model choice:** Declaration of the fundamental matrix based on target dynamics, choosing between Constant Position (CP), Constant Velocity (CV), or Constant Acceleration (CA).
- **Association settings:** The chosen bipartite matching algorithm (Greedy or Hungarian via SciPy) and the likelihood metric (Standard Mahalanobis, size-modulated Mahalanobis, or GloU-calibrated precision matrix with pre-defined constants).

3.5.3.4 Results

According to our evaluation, the size-modulated association metric performs better than GloU. Due to simplicity of the size-modulated metric, the implementation was possible to fully vectorize. The calculational speed is 15 to 25 times faster than our best take on the heading-only GloU. This translates to about 3x faster tracking of the nuScenes data. Apart from the speed and simplicity, the association quality is quite improved comparing to that of the heading-only GloU used for calibration. For example, in tracking of the 10 scenes from the nuScenes mini subset of annotations, we are getting F1-score 0.949305 (TP 18108 TN 1778 FP 64 FN 1870) for the heading-only GloU and 0.986791 (TP 18341 TN 1681 FP 62 FN 429) for the size-modulated metric we propose.

3.5.3.5 Conclusions

This work successfully addresses the fundamental challenges of object identification and kinematic state estimation in the context of self-driving Multiple-Object Tracking (MOT). The key contributions and conclusions are summarized below:

- **Elimination of Manual Tuning:** The developed original adaptive process-noise model effectively eliminates the traditional, ad-hoc tuning requirement for linear Kalman filters. By utilizing instant values of derivatives via finite differences and running averages, the model achieves optimal tracking responsiveness across varying motion dynamics (CP, CV, and CA models).
- **Superior Computational Efficiency:** By abandoning complex geometric calculations in favor of a fully vectorized, size-modulated Mahalanobis precision matrix, the proposed

association metric achieves processing speeds 15 to 25 times faster than the heading-only GloU baseline. This computational leap translates directly to a 3x faster overall tracking pipeline when processing nuScenes data.

- **Enhanced Tracking Accuracy:** Beyond its computational advantages and lower implementation complexity, the size-modulated metric demonstrably improves tracking quality over purely geometric alternatives. Quantitative evaluation on the nuScenes mini dataset yielded a significant reduction in False Negatives and advanced the tracking F1-score.
- **Open-Source Accessibility:** The entire framework is production-ready and accessible to the community. The core algorithm is distributed via the main Python registry as kinematic-tracker.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable consolidates the outcomes of work conducted in WP4 to establish a coherent foundation for semantic interoperability and structured data handling in advanced traffic and mobility systems. The work includes the harmonisation of data formats, the creation of an Ontology Catalogue, the development of standardised tool description and specification templates, the definition of a tool vocabulary and tool ontology, and the implementation of an ontology management service. Together, these elements provide a consistent semantic framework that enables the integration of heterogeneous tools and datasets across the SYNERGIES ecosystem.

In addition, the deliverable incorporates contributions from Task 4.2, addressing data fusion, semantic abstraction, and compression for complex and extended scenarios. By building on the semantic foundations established in WP4, the Task 4.2 activities support efficient representation and handling of spatio-temporal scenario data while preserving semantic consistency and interpretability. These concepts contribute to scalable processing of complex traffic scenarios and support their reuse within simulation and validation workflows.

The results presented advance the state of the art by introducing a structured and standards-oriented approach to semantic interoperability, tool-level integration, and scenario data handling. The combined outcomes of Tasks 4.1 and 4.2 ensure consistency, traceability, and extensibility across tools and work packages, providing a robust basis for scenario generation, execution, and evaluation within the SYNERGIES platform.

Overall, this deliverable establishes a solid and integrated semantic framework that supports interoperable workflows and efficient management of complex scenario data. These results form a key enabler for subsequent platform integration, validation, and deployment activities, and underpin the effective use of SYNERGIES tools across multiple use cases. With respect to data compression, the semantic fusion and compression models developed in T4.2 address this objective at a conceptual and methodological level in this deliverable; their full implementation as integrated toolchain components is planned for subsequent tasks T4.3–T4.5 and will be reported in D4.2

5 REFERENCES

- [1] Gasparic I. et al. (2025). D5.1 – Scenario Ontology and Semantic Framework. Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action. Grant Agreement No. 101146542
- [2] Revert E. et al (2025). D2.2 – Data Quality and Metadata Specifications. Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action, Grant Agreement No. 101146542.
- [3] ASAM e.V., ASAM OpenDRIVE®, Version 1.8.1.https://publications.pages.asam.net/standards/ASAM_OpenDRIVE/ASAM_OpenDRIVE_Specification/latest/specification/index.html
- [4] ASAM e.V., ASAM OSI, Version 3.7.0 – GroundTruth messages.https://opensimulationinterface.github.io/osi-antora-generator/asamosi/latest/gen/structosi3_1_1GroundTruth.html
- [5] MCAP – A Modular Container Format for Logged Robotics and Autonomous Vehicle Data. Available at: <https://mcap.dev/> [Accessed: 05-12-2025].
- [6] GitHub, Omega-Prime: Data Model, Data Format and Python Library for Ground Truth Traffic Data. Available at: <https://github.com/ika-rwth-aachen/omega-prime> [Accessed: 30.12.2025]<https://github.com/ika-rwth-aachen/omega-prime>
- [7] Protégé Ontology Editor. Available at: <https://protege.stanford.edu/software.php> [Accessed: 30.12.2025]
- [8] ASAM e.V., ASAM OpenODD® Base Standard, Version 1.0.0, April 2025. Available at: https://publications.pages.asam.net/standards/ASAM_OpenODD/ASAM_OpenODD/latest/specification/index.html [Accessed: 30.12.2025]
- [9] ASAM e.V., „ASAM OpenXOntology“ [Online]. Available at: <https://www.asam.net/standards/asam-openxontology/> [Accessed: 05.12.2025]
- [10] ASAM e.V., „ASAM OpenLABEL“ [Online]. Available at: <https://www.asam.net/standards/detail/openlabel> [Accessed: 05.12.2025]
- [11] Beckmann, J., Zhang, X., de Gelder, E., van Hassel, E., Nieto, M., Ben Nejma, G., & Grabowski, M. (2025). *D5.2 – Harmonised descriptions for content of CCAM safety assessment data framework*. SUNRISE – Safety assurance framework for connected, automated mobility Systems. Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action, Grant Agreement No. 101069573.
- [12] SAE International, SAE J3016 – Taxonomy and Definitions for Terms Related to Driving Automation Systems, 2021.
- [13] British Standards Institution (BSI), PAS 1881:2020 – Assurance of Safety-Related AI Systems, 2020.
- [14] International Organization for Standardization (ISO), ISO 34504 – Road Vehicles – Scenario-Based Safety Evaluation, 2022.
- [15] Dal'Col, L., Oliveira, F., & Santos, M., Semantic modelling of traffic scenarios for automated driving, IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference (ITSC), 2024.
- [16] Huang, X., et al., A unified representation for multi-sensor traffic scenarios, IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles, 2024.
- [17] Web Ontology Language (OWL): <https://www.w3.org/OWL/> [Accessed: 30.12.2025]

- [18] Ontotext GraphDB – RDF and Knowledge Graph Database, Available at: <https://www.ontotext.com/products/graphdb/> [Accessed: 30.12.2025]
- [19] Urbietta, I., Mujika, A., Piérola, G., Irigoyen, E., Nieto, M., Loyo, E., & Aginako, N. (2023). WebLabel: OpenLABEL-compliant multi-sensor labelling. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-023-16664-4>
- [20] Jeyachandran, Jerein, Khastgir, Siddartha, Zhao, Xingyu, Barbier, Eric and Jennings, Paul. A. (2025) *Introducing OASISS : ODD-based AI Safety In autonomouS Systems*. In: The IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC), Gold Coast, Australia, 18-21 Nov 2025 (In Press)
- [21] GitHub, GLIM versatile and extensible range-based 3D mapping framework. Available at: <https://github.com/koide3/glim> [Accessed: 11.05.2026]
- [22] GTSAM Factor graphs for Sensor Fusion in Robotics. Available at: <https://gtsam.org/> [Accessed: 11.05.2026]
- [23] Biber, P., & Strasser, W. (2003). The Normal Distributions Transform: A New Approach to Laser Scan Matching. Proceedings of the IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS 2003).
- [24] Liu, Y., Wang, T., Zhang, X., Chen, Y., Wang, J., & Xiong, H. (2023). BEVFusion: A Simple and Robust LiDAR–Camera Fusion Framework. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS 2023)*.
- [25] Lynch, K., Mohan, R., Battiato, S., & IEEE (2018). The DriveU Traffic Light Dataset for Autonomous Driving. Proceedings of the IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV 2018).
- [26] Github, Kinematic tracker. Available at: <https://koyalp.github.io/kinematic-tracker-docs/> [Accessed: 12.05.2026]
- [27] Koval, P., Aranjuelo Ansa, N., Javierre del Rio, P., & Menendez Arechalde, A. (2026). Simple evaluation of association quality in tracking-by-detection. Available at: <https://www.researchsquare.com/article/rs-9150527/v1> [Accessed: 12.05.2026]

A. ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS

Term	Definition
ASAM	Association for Standardisation of Automation and Measuring Systems
CA	Constant Acceleration (motion model for Kalman filtering)
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility
CP	Constant Position (motion model for Kalman filtering)
CV	Constant Velocity (motion model for Kalman filtering)
GloU	Generalised Intersection over Union
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
ICP	Iterative Closest Point (scan-matching algorithm)
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IoU	Intersection over Union
IRLS	Iteratively Reweighted Least Squares
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KKT	Karush–Kuhn–Tucker (optimality conditions)
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
MCAP	Modular Container Format for Autonomous and Robotics Data
MHE	Moving Horizon Estimation
MOT / MTT	Multiple-Object Tracking / Multiple-Target Tracking
NDT	Normal Distributions Transform
ODD	Operational Design Domain
OWL	Web Ontology Language (W3C standard)
PCRS	Point Cloud Reference System
POM	PROVEN Ontology Manager
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package
xosc	OpenSCENARIO file extension (.xosc)